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Table of Contents

GENERAL DATA	2
Table of Contents	4
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	7
List of Abbreviations	8
ABSTRACT	10
1. Introduction	14
1.1 Aim of this report	14
1.2 Background	14
1.3 Main objectives	18
2. Methods	19
3. Soil Management Strategy Categories	23
3.1 Tillage Management	23
3.2 Cropping Systems	33
3.3 Water Management	44
3.4 Fertilization and Organic matter input	51
3.4.1 Crop Residues	51
3.4.2 Cover crop (Green manure)	56
3.4.3 Livestock manure, slurry and compost	62
3.4.4 Biochar	73
3.4.5 Liming	79
4. Summary and Conclusion	85
4.1 Current knowledge (gaps) on trade-offs and synergies on specific soil management strategy categories	85
4.2 Knowledge gaps and research recommendations	89
4.3 Limitations of this report	92
5. Bibliography	93

List of Tables

Table 1: Most important soil management strategies in EU agriculture as considered by the Σ OMMIT consortium. These strategies are grouped per soil management strategy category (in bold).....	19
Table 2: Land use types considered as important in Europe and used as a selection criteria during literature screening.	20
Table 3: Number of literature items that describe the effects of a soil management strategy category on trade-offs, synergies, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching, carbon sequestration or micro-organisms or a combination of these topics. Note that a single literature item can describe the effects of multiple soil management strategy categories and that it can be included more than once per category if it describes multiple soil management practices. Between brackets the number of the most relevant literature items that are included in this report can be found.	21
Table 4: Example of the first table that is constructed for each section and subsection of chapter 3. For each literature item that describes the effect of a soil management strategy on the parameters mentioned in italic in the title row a new row is foreseen in which a color code indicates the impact compared to business as usual or other soil management strategies as indicated in the figure legends. A green cell indicates a positive effect, a red cell a negative effect and a grey cell indicates a neutral effect. For each literature item it is indicated in superscript if it concerns a meta-analysis (1), review (2) or an original paper (3). In the summary row an overview is given of the general effects of the specific soil management strategy category.....	22
Table 5: The effect of reduced tillage intensity on SOC sequestration, GHG balances (CO ₂ eq.), N ₂ O, CO ₂ , and CH ₄ , emissions, and N leaching losses. No-tillage and non-inversion tillage are compared to the conventional inversion tillage (ploughing).....	26
Table 6: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on tillage (RT, NT and CON)	28
Table 7: List of cropping systems considered in the present overview. Terminology, description, and remarks of cropping systems have been adapted from Azam-Ali (2003) and Francis and Porter (2017).	34
Table 8: The impact of cropping systems listed in Table 7 on changes in SOC stock, microbial C biomass (MBC), microbial N biomass (MBN), N ₂ O, CH ₄ , and CO ₂ emissions, and N leaching. Crop rotation is compared to monocropping, agro-forestry to arable systems, and organic agriculture to conventional/conservation agriculture.....	39
Table 9: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on cropping systems	42
Table 10: The effect of irrigation on SOC, GHG emissions and N leaching losses compared to rainfed systems.....	46
Table 11: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles irrigation	47
Table 12: The effect of crop residue returns on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), and GHG emissions and N leaching losses compared to residues removal.	52
Table 13: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on residues returns (incorporation or surface application)	53

Table 14: The effect of non-legume and legume cover crops on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N ₂ O and CO ₂ , and N leaching losses compared to no cover crops.	57
Table 15: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on cover crops (CC)	58
Table 16: The effect of adding manure, slurry and compost on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N ₂ O and CO ₂ compared to no fertilization (*) or mineral fertilization (**)	65
<i>Table 17: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on manure, slurry and compost.</i>	<i>68</i>
Table 18: The effect of biochar on SOC change, N ₂ O and CH ₄ emission and uptake and NO ₃ leaching losses compared to control soil without biochar.	75
Table 19: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses and reviews on biochar.....	76
Table 20: The impact of liming (lime, dolomite, olivine, zeolite, sugar beet lime with red gypsum) on SOC sequestration, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N ₂ O and CO ₂ , and N leaching losses compared to no amendment.....	81
Table 21: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on liming	82
Table 22: The effect of soil management strategies on SOC change, GHG emissions, microbial biomass nitrogen and carbon, and N leaching.	88

List of Figures

Figure 1: General step-by-step plan that was used to collect literature, process literature, extract relevant information from literature and to compile this report. 20

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AC	Annual cropping
AGF	Agroforestry
BEC	Bioenergy crops
C	Carbon
C/N ratio	Carbon to nitrogen ratio
CC	Cover crops
CF	Land use change from cropland to forestry
CG	Land use change from cropland to grassland
CL	Cropland
CONS	Conservation agriculture
CONV	Conventional agriculture
CTC	Catch crops
CV	Coefficient of variation
DIV	Crop diversification
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
DRC	Deep-rooting crops
EC	European commission
EF	Emission factor
EU	European Union
FC	Land use change from forestry to cropland
GC	Land use change from grassland to cropland
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GL	Grassland
GRASS BS	Grass buffer strips
HEDG	Hedges
LEG	Legumes
LI	Low-input
LSD	Least significant difference
LTEs	Long-term experiments
MBC	Microbial biomass carbon
MBN	Microbial biomass nitrogen
MON	Monocropping

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

MULT	Multiple cropping
N leaching	Nitrogen leaching
N/A	Not assessed
NFC	N-fixing crops
N	Nitrogen
OAs	Organic amendments
OM	Organic matter
ORG	Organic agriculture
PAS	Permanent pasture
PER	Permanent cropping
RB	Riparian buffers
RCMPs	Recommended carbon management practices
ROT	Crop rotation
SAR	Sodium adsorption ratio
SAS	Silvo-arable systems
SD	Standard deviation
SE	Standard error
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SOM	Soil organic matter
TLD	Temporary leys of longer duration

ABSTRACT

Carbon sequestration in agricultural soil is a strategy to mitigate climate change which is gaining attention. Appropriate soil management strategies are crucial to obtain a sustainable increase and maintenance of soil organic carbon (SOC) levels. A number of soil management strategies have already been shown to successfully contribute to an increased SOC content in agricultural soils. However, these soil management strategies may also stimulate the production of the potent greenhouse gasses nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄) and may induce increased losses of N (nitrogen) via leaching. These trade-offs can offset the climate change mitigation that was intended via carbon sequestration. Nevertheless, synergies may also occur, with a stronger effect on the mitigation potential of certain soil management strategies. Despite the major importance of these trade-offs and synergies for the selection of sustainable and climate-proof soil management strategies, specific knowledge on these effects remains limited, particularly for Europe. Therefore, the SOMMIT-project aims to investigate the most relevant soil management strategies applied in European agricultural systems for their impact on SOC and on the emission of greenhouse gasses (GHG) or N leaching.

With this report, we provide an overview of existing knowledge gaps on the effects of important soil management strategies on trade-offs and synergies between SOC sequestration on the one hand and N₂O- and CH₄- emissions and N leaching on the other hand. We also identified and compiled research recommendations that may assist in gaining more insight in these trade-offs and synergies. In addition, despite the scarce literature and fragmented knowledge for Europe, this report provides a summary of the state-of-the-art of the knowledge on these trade-offs and synergies. In this way, the report brings together both current knowledge about the trade-offs and synergies, but also presents an indication of the general effects of important European soil management strategies on both carbon sequestration, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching and microbial biomass carbon (MBC) and nitrogen (MBN). The compilation of these effects gives unique and novel insights on the impact of different soil management strategy categories on potential trade-offs and synergies. In combination with the identified knowledge gaps and research recommendations this provides a unique basis to help to (re-)design dedicated experiments to improve our understandings of these impacts.

This report was compiled via a dedicated literature study performed by eight agricultural research institutes spread over Europe. The most important European agricultural soil management systems were identified and grouped into four categories: tillage management, cropping systems, water management and fertilization and OM inputs. Literature was screened for the effects of the specified soil management strategies on both the trade-offs and synergies between carbon sequestration and GHG emissions or nitrogen leaching. Specific effects on carbon sequestration, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching, and microbial biomass carbon and nitrogen were considered as well. The use of search restrictions on type of literature, land use, time-period, and research origin resulted in a unique selection of 110 literature items. After literature processing, collection of meta-data and the extraction of knowledge gaps, research recommendations and the main conclusions, these were stored in a knowledge (gap) template, in which also the partners personal comments were listed. The latter template served as the basis for this combined report on knowledge gaps and literature review on the effect of management practices on C sequestration, N₂O and CH₄ fluxes and N leaching losses.

For each soil management strategy category multiple knowledge gaps and research recommendations could be identified:

Tillage management – While no tillage and non-inversion tillage in general positively affect SOC stocks in the 0-30 cm soil layer, the effects on whole profile SOC storage are still not well understood. Information about the effects on SOC stocks in the subsoils is largely missing and therefore more

attention for subsoils is required in experimental set-ups aiming at investigating the effects of soil management strategies on SOC stocks. At this moment, there are still conflicting results on how different tillage systems affect the N₂O emissions. To better understand the trade-offs or relation with the emission (or uptake) of GHG, these emissions need to be studied when a combination of different soil management practices is applied such as different cropping systems, crop residue management and cover crops adoption. In this way more insights can be obtained in the interaction effects of practices relevant for the agricultural sector. Furthermore, more research is required on the impact of tillage management on nitrogen leaching since the number of studies describing this effect are limited.

Cropping systems – It is well-known that application of combined crop sequences and soil management practices such as crop rotation and the use of legumes with conservation tillage or organic agricultural systems can enhance SOC storage. Nevertheless, the impact of other cropping systems (e.g., agroforestry) on SOC storage cannot be accurately quantified yet because of the lack of a complete understanding of above- and below-ground biomass C storage (in e.g., trees and/or shrubs). Furthermore, there is a need to improve the understanding of how the translocation of carbon and nutrients but also belowground plant biomass of different cropping systems contributes to soil SOC stock changes.

The C sequestration potential of relatively new management practices such as agroforestry (but also organic farming) is not conclusive because published SOC stock data on long-term field experiments in different pedo-climatic zones are lacking, and more specific studies are recommended. A better understanding of the management practices applied in these systems may contribute to a stimulation of SOC stocks. Furthermore, the effects on SOC stocks may be influenced by other combined management practices (e.g., crop residues, cover crops, fertilization, and tillage) and environmental factors (pedoclimatic conditions) of which the impact requires more research.

Concerning N₂O emissions, it is indicated that permanent cropping systems in conservation and organic agriculture can reduce N₂O emissions compared to annual cropping systems. The impact of cropping systems on N₂O emissions depends on the type of cropping system. As a consequence, the effects on the trade-offs between N₂O emissions and SOC are variable. Despite the relative contribution of N₂O emissions to the total GHG emission arising from cropland is low, N₂O emissions are highly important for the total GHG balance. Therefore, soil borne GHG emissions arising from different cropping systems require more in-depth studies to fully understand the impact on the trade-offs. Furthermore, there is a need to study these effects in different pedoclimatic conditions. Likewise, there is also a need to study the impact of more and different cropping systems on CH₄ emissions and N leaching since at this moment only the impact of a limited number of cropping systems is investigated. In organic agriculture, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions but also NO₃ leaching were reduced in organic agricultural systems. Furthermore, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions were also reduced when using an agroforestry system and crop rotations, respectively.

Water management – Irrigation generally stimulates the SOC content. The combination of irrigation with conservation tillage stimulates SOC contents. However, since climate, soil conditions, crop and residue management and soil management may impact this stimulation, further research is needed. These impacts may depend on the irrigation technique (flood, furrow, sprinkler, drip) and environmental factors (climate, soil condition, crop and residue management). This report indicates that irrigation induces trade-offs mainly with direct and indirect N₂O emissions (i.e., N₂O emissions and NO₃- leaching). Despite this, the effect on the trade-offs between C sequestration and GHG emissions is very uncertain as well as the impact on CH₄ emissions in upland soils. Research on the impact of different irrigation practices on N₂O and CH₄ emissions in the various European pedo-climatic zones is limited. Likewise, literature on the trade-offs and synergies is very scarce. Such studies are very

relevant and could provide better insights into the trade-offs between GHG emission/N leaching and C-sequestration. In addition, the impact of irrigation related to the emissions associated to constructed water bodies used for irrigation is poorly understood and requires more in-depth research.

Fertilization and organic matter (OM) inputs – The studied OM inputs (crop residues, cover crops, manure, slurry, compost, biochar) but also other fertilization materials such as liming products tend to stimulate the SOC content in soils. Still, only a limited number of studies is available that investigate the impact of the OM inputs on nitrogen leaching. The quality of OM inputs and the pedo-climatic conditions need to be studied more in depth, as they moderate the outcomes.

Crop residues: Despite the impact of incorporation of straw on SOC stock increases is well studied globally and in Europe, the impact on N₂O emissions is still controversial. While straw C/N ratio is the main factor determining the accumulation of SOC as well as the variability of the N₂O emission and NO₃⁻ leaching after residue addition, more research on the impact of the straw quality and quantity is recommended. In addition, the impact of straw return on nitrogen leaching losses are less studied and no European synthesis on this topic exists. Furthermore, the impact of pedo-climatic factors is still poorly understood. The quality of meta-analyses needs to be improved, since a problem with non-independence of effect sizes and unweighted procedures, which were common for the meta-analyses on straw return, may cause overestimation of results.

Cover crop: Trade-offs and synergies mostly depend on the type of CC and GHG. Indeed, as for non-legume CC, trade-offs between SOC increase and GHG emissions were demonstrated for CO₂, but not for N₂O. In contrast, a synergy was reported between SOC increase and N leaching reduction of 50% on average, both globally as for some regions in EU. For legume CC, a positive impact on SOC was accompanied by stimulated GHG emissions but no N leaching reduction. However, since there is no meta-analysis summarizing the effects of cover crops on SOC, N₂O emissions and N leaching losses across Europe, this is a knowledge gap that requires research.

Livestock manure, slurry and compost: The well investigated impact of manure, slurry and compost on SOC reveals a positive impact on the SOC stock change. However, the impact on N₂O and CO₂ emissions and N leaching is poorly understood. Since there are only a limited number of European publications that focused on emissions in field experiments, it is therefore required to study the impact of these OM inputs on N₂O and CO₂ emissions and N leaching via field experiments in different European pedoclimatic zones. Indeed, this report reveals a variety of effects (negative, neutral, positive) on N₂O emissions which clearly indicates the need for further research. In addition, many authors point out that some important data (properties of OM inputs, soil properties) that are crucial for a holistic understanding of the topic, are missing in current literature and requires attention in future publications.

Biochar: Biochar is a promising OM amendment to increase the soil carbon content. Furthermore, biochar application to soil is known to reduce N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching. However, there is uncertainty about the impact of biochar on CH₄ uptake in upland soils which require more research. In addition, more knowledge is required about the impact of how biochar impacts native soil organic carbon levels and N cycling over time which should be investigated in long term field experiments. Due to the high variability of existing biochar types and their functioning in different soils, it is important that the most relevant properties of different biochar types are characterized. This will allow the selection of the best suited biochar for different agronomic and environmental purposes.

Liming: Application of liming most often results in a stimulation of SOC stocks. This seems to be an indirect effect of a higher C input to limed soils due to increased crop biomass productivity. The stimulation of the plant growth but also of soil microorganisms inevitably increases the CO₂ flux through soil respiration. However, this negative impact might be outweighed by increasing SOC stocks. However, decreases of the SOC stock level have been reported as well, probably caused by a stimulated

mineralization. Therefore, more research on the impact of liming on SOC stocks but also the role of improved soil structure herein is required. In addition, the effects of liming on plant inputs to the soil, which affect the overall carbon balance, needs specific further investigations.

The impact on N₂O emission mitigation is positive since liming stimulates N₂O reduction to N₂ and enhances plant growth and plant N uptake. Research focusing on the effect on trade-offs and synergies (carbon sequestration, N₂O and CH₄ emissions and N leaching) is lacking. For this, long-term field experiments are required to investigate the effects of different liming amendments. Finally, these effects need to be studied in combination with other soil management strategies.

In general, more dedicated research is needed for all soil management strategies that simultaneously examines SOC stocks, GHG emissions and nitrogen leaching losses. Furthermore, this report identified the lack of information on the impact of pedoclimatic conditions on the trade-offs and synergies. More insights need to be obtained in field experiments in different pedo-climatic European regions where the long-term effects can be studied, since knowledge about these effects is very scarce, yet essential for a comprehensive understanding of the impact of soil management strategies. Ideally, the impact of soil management practices from one strategy category (tillage management, cropping systems, water management, fertilization and OM input) can be studied in combination with soil management practices of other categories. Indeed, since soil management strategies are often combined their interaction which may affect the trade-offs and synergies must be considered.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of this report

One of the main objectives of the European Joint Programme **EJP SOIL** (www.ejpsoil.org) is to enhance the contribution of agricultural soils to key societal challenges such as climate change adaptation and mitigation. Via the Σ OMMIT-project, an evaluation of the trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, N₂O and CH₄ emissions, and nitrate losses will be made. More specifically, the impact of soil management strategies aiming to stimulate soil organic carbon (SOC) storage on these trade-offs and synergies will be assessed. Only the most important European agricultural soil management strategies were considered, and four categories were identified: tillage management, cropping system, water management and fertilization and OM inputs. For these soil management strategies, the existing knowledge gaps and the current knowledge available on both the impact on the trade-offs and synergies are compiled in this report. This report will serve as a comprehensive basis to design dedicated experiments and targeted measurements or simulations in other work packages (WP3, WP4) of the Σ OMMIT-project.

1.2 Background

SOC stock is a very important soil quality indicator that directly affects soil functions and ecosystem services. SOC stock reflects the long-term balance between C inputs (i.e., rhizodeposition, crop residues, and exogenous organic products) and C losses by mineralization and leaching. Its loss represents one of the most important soil threats as addressed in the Soil Thematic Strategy (EC, 2006). Globally, SOC in agricultural soils is undergoing substantial change due to environmental conditions (e.g., temperature and precipitation patterns), land use/cover changes, and management effects (Hu et al., 2018; Tiefenbacher et al., 2021). It is well-known that the conversion of grasslands and forests to cropland have increased the mineralization process of soil organic matter (SOM) and significantly decreased SOC stocks which contributed to an increased carbon dioxide (CO₂) emission to the atmosphere (Janzen et al., 2004).

Increasing SOC stocks by proper management may bring beneficial effects to crop productivity and the environment, as well as contribute to climate change mitigation by a reduction of agricultural GHG emissions. This can be achieved by reducing C mineralization and thus CO₂ emissions but also by increasing carbon sinks (Paustian et al., 2016) or a combination of these factors.

In the last decades, the function of SOC in mitigating climate change has been identified as a sustainable and cost-effective strategy (Wijesekara et al., 2021). It has been estimated that the global rate of SOC sequestration ranges between 0.4-1.2 gigatons annually, by adopting recommended C management practices (RCMPs) (Lal, 2004). SOC sequestration refers to the storage of C in the soil in the medium- and long-term (15 to 50 years) (Goh, 2011). The maintenance or increase of current SOC stocks is primarily managed through soil C inputs (e.g., retention of harvested crop residues, application of organic manures or biosolids), by adopting RCMP, which include organic and conservation agriculture, agroforestry, and application of external organic materials into the soils. Moreover, other agricultural management practices that contribute to minimize soil disturbance and erosion (e.g., conservation tillage, the use of crop rotations and cover crops) can maximize crop residues retained on the soil surface as well as increase soil water storage and nutrient use efficiencies of cropping systems (Jarecki and Lal, 2003). Overall, the intensity and type of management practice adopted directly influence the SOC stocks of agricultural soils (Rumpel et al., 2020).

Recent emphasis on promoting SOC storage has resulted in the '4 per mil' international initiative launched during the UNFCCC conference of the parties (COP) 21 by France. Increasing global agricultural SOC stocks at an annual rate of 4‰ would result in a C sequestration potential of 2-3 Pg C/year as showed by preliminary evaluations (Minasny et al., 2017). Thus, even very small increases per unit area in the SOC pool can have important positive implications in the global C balance and climate change since it may offset a significant fraction of CO₂ emissions worldwide (Guenet et al., 2021).

Since it is well known that C cycle is tightly coupled with the N cycle, we can assume that the deployment of land-based mitigation options to increase SOC may directly affect the N cycle and the associated N losses, particularly N₂O emissions and NO₃⁻ leaching, which contribute to global warming and groundwater contamination, respectively.

The N₂O emissions are mainly derived from microbial turnover of N inputs to agricultural land, i.e., chemical fertilizers, manure, urine deposited by grazing animals, and of residues of leguminous crops. Increasing the SOC content may thus enhance the risk of stimulated N₂O emissions due to the tight link between SOC and microbial N₂O production. As reported by Hansen et al. (2019), the impact of SOC on N₂O emissions is also influenced by the soil NO₃⁻ content. It is thus important to evaluate how the supply of N and C inputs addresses the N₂O emissions in cropping systems.

The NO₃⁻ leaching is an abiotic process, where NO₃ is transported out of the root zone along with the downward water flow (Hansen et al., 2019). The leaching rate is highly influenced by soil water content, texture, and soil structure. Extreme rainfall events and/or periods of drought can significantly affect leaching. Particularly, NO₃⁻ can easily be lost from the agroecosystem by leaching during periods with high drainage rates due to its high mobility in soil. A well-developed active root system enhances NO₃⁻ uptake, whereas a poor root system will not utilize all the NO₃⁻ within the soil profile.

For this report, the most important European agricultural soil management strategies were selected that have been investigated in European studies. These were grouped in four soil management strategy categories: tillage management, cropping systems, water management, fertilization and OM inputs.

Tillage management

Conventional tillage such as deep ploughing mechanically destroys soil aggregates on the soil surface and favors microbial SOM decomposition (Tiefenbacher et al., 2021). Excessive tillage such as moldboard ploughing limits the potential benefits of agricultural systems to increase SOC stocks. Compared to less intensive tillage practices, deep inversion tillage reduces SOC storage because it accelerates decomposition of crop residues via physical destruction and mixture into the soil. To date, several reviews and meta-analyses have already demonstrated both beneficial and null effects of reduced tillage intensity/no-tillage on SOC content, but there is still a need for a comprehensive systematic review to answer the question: What are the effects of tillage intensity on SOC and the trade-offs of GHG emissions and N leaching. Therefore, in this report we focus specially on papers that evaluate the impact of tillage on the SOC content and these trade-offs (GHG and N leaching).

Cropping systems

Cropping system refers to the type and sequence of crops and the soil management practices (e.g., tillage systems, crop residue management, fertilization and OM inputs, pest and disease control, water management, and soil conservation) on agricultural fields over time (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2008). These systems have been traditionally designed to maximize crop yields, but - considering the

emerging social, economic, and ecological or environmental concerns - modern agriculture is promoting a re-design of cropping systems towards a more sustainable agricultural system. Diversification of crops and well-designed cropping systems are important strategies to improve soil properties and promote soil fertility such as biological activity and nutrient cycling. The selection and design of cropping practices are a function of soil, management, and climatic conditions.

In this context, agroforestry - combining woody perennials (e.g., trees and shrubs) with agricultural crop or grassland - generally fulfils multiple ecological (such as increased SOC stocks, improved soil fertility) and socioeconomic (e.g., higher crop productivity and the provision of crops) services. Also, organic agriculture compared to conventional agriculture can improve C sequestration rate and reduce GHG emissions. However, the effects of cropping systems managed under organic versus conventional agriculture on SOC stock changes has long been debated (e.g., Leifeld et al., 2013) because SOC stock under organic agriculture may also decrease or remain unaffected compared to the conventional agricultural systems (Drinkwater et al., 1998; Green et al., 2005). The main reasons for these inconsistencies are due to a wide range of interacting factors such as tillage practices, type of C inputs, cropping systems, climate, and soil properties (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2008).

Water management

Irrigation and water management practices are important to supply water for crops and to adapt agriculture to overcome the water deficiency due to climate change and the lack of reliable rainfall (Trost et al., 2013). Irrigation increases plant-available water in soils and helps to increase net primary production and C inputs into soil in dry environmental conditions. In this way, irrigation indirectly impacts the evolution of SOC stocks. Irrigation itself might thus affect climate by altering the capacity of soils to act as a C sink or source but can also impact the emission of N₂O (Lal 2004). Indeed, despite the increased plant C inputs into soil favored by irrigation, an accelerated C and N mineralization due to the combined effects with other management practices such as tillage might reduce the benefits of irrigation for SOC stocks and favor detrimental effects (Tiefenbacher et al., 2021).

Fertilization and OM inputs

It is well known that the application of fertilization and organic matter (OM) inputs such as organic amendments (OAs) to agricultural land are appropriate practices to improve the soil organic matter (SOM) content and to aid the recycling of nutrients (e.g; straw that would be burnt otherwise, compost, manure) (Pezzolla et al., 2012). Hence, the application of organic materials has multiple roles in improving soil physical, chemical, and biological properties, by providing benefits linked to the reduction of soil erosion and to the enhancement of soil quality. However, it is also known that the excessive application of organic materials to agricultural soils can increase GHG emissions. Actual effects of external organic materials on soil quality, SOC stock changes, and nutrient cycling may be detected over long periods (Diacono and Montemurro, 2010).

Soil OAs comprise animal manures (e.g., slurry), crop residues, green manures, compost, and agro-industrial wastes (Aguilera et al., 2013a). They can be either left on the soil surface or incorporated into the soil. Applying amendments on the soil surface is especially effective when used in combination with the conservation tillage systems as opposed to traditional practices where amendments are plowed into soil. The application of OAs enhances plant growth by improving soil structure, increasing water retention, and replenishing nutrients for plants. They are also important substrates of C and N for microbial growth, and they may stimulate microbial activity involved in N assimilation or N₂O production and NO₃⁻ availability (Charles et al., 2017). Conversely, the absence of organic fertilizer inputs determined a decrease in SOC stock and soil quality, with a higher percentage of non-complex and lightweight humus.

In this context, solid and liquid animal manures (from sheep, cattle, and poultry) are rich in organic matter and macro- and micro-nutrients, essential to improve crop production, soil structure, and water holding capacity and to enhance the fertility of agricultural soils (Tiefenbacher et al., 2021). Manure application promotes a range of microbial processes essential for soil functioning. When managed properly, manure reduces demands for fertilizers, improves crop productivity, and limit N losses such as N₂O emissions and NO₃⁻ leaching. However, the recycling of cattle farming byproducts for CO₂ sequestration purposes poses environmental risks such as pollution by NO₃⁻ leaching, that can reduce its sustainability in agricultural land (Diacono and Montemurro, 2010).

Compost consists mostly of plant-based material (e.g., biowaste) or sewage-sludge, which is decomposed under aerobic conditions in a controlled environment. Some authors reported that continuous compost application in the field increase the total humus content (Diacono and Montemurro, 2010). In the last decades, scientific knowledge on composting has notably increased and the technology to treat and stabilize organic matter is improved. Nevertheless, the production of GHG emissions, particularly CH₄ and N₂O, seems to be unavoidable. Therefore, the selection of proper management conditions (e.g., source and duration of the maturation phase) plays a key role to determine the magnitude of such emissions (Pardo et al., 2015) as well as the quality and composition of the final compost (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2008).

The maintenance of crop residues into the field provides numerous ecosystem services and is useful for SOC sequestration, nutrient cycling (e.g., N, P, K, S, micronutrients), soil erosion control, and improvement of soil structure and hydraulic properties. Specifically, their primary functions are to conserve water and improve fertility in soils. Conversely, removal of crop residues for other use (e.g., biofuel production) can negatively impact soil properties by reducing SOM inputs, increasing GHG emissions by altering water and nutrient cycling.

The use of cover crops is an innovative and promising conservation practice, specifically promoted as a practice to be combined with conservation tillage (no-tillage and reduced tillage), cropping systems (e.g., alley cropping, crop rotation, and agroforestry), and other conservation practices designed to improve crop yield, soil quality, and water resources as well as to recycle nutrients, reduce GHG emissions, and prevent NO₃⁻ leaching and soil erosion. Cover crops have multiple benefits, so their use is highly desirable. They are mainly grown between the cropping seasons, but they can also be grown as crops in rotation or intercropped to main crops. Legume cover crops supplement N fertilization by fixing N₂ from the atmosphere, while non-legume cover crops exploit the residual N left after harvest of the main crop (Sandén et al. 2018). The most recent trend is to terminate cover crop as mulch (i.e., left at the soil surface as living mulch or flattened by no-tillage roller crimper) rather than incorporating it into the soil as green manure.

In a recent meta-analysis, Borchard et al. (2019) reported biochar as a promising organic C amendment - characterized by different fractions of C (small, easy mineralizing and a more recalcitrant C) - for limiting soil NO₃⁻ leaching and for improving soil quality. Therefore, the application of biochar to soils may affect factors that control nitrification, denitrification, and other N transformation pathways. In this context, meta-analyses have been found to be a useful tool in order to assess the potential and magnitude of biochar for reducing N losses and increasing SOC stock of agricultural systems (Borenstein et al., 2009).

Other amendments such as the inorganic ones (e.g., lime) perform specific functions by reducing soil acidity or increasing pH. Anaerobic digestion and sludge are two other promising external organic materials that can be applied in agricultural soils, but only few studies have been conducted and are therefore not included in this report.

As stated by Diacono and Montemurro (2010), the effects of application of OM inputs on soil quality and fertility should not be restricted to a simple quantification of SOC stock or CO₂ balance, but they must consider all GHG fluxes by including sources and sinks across the soil-plant system. To date, there is a strong need to better understand the GHG fluxes as related to organic material input dynamics in the agricultural soils.

1.3 Main objectives

This report aims at synthesizing existing knowledge, knowledge gaps and research recommendations considering the impact of important European soil management strategies on the trade-offs and synergies between soil carbon sequestration on the one hand and non-CO₂ GHG fluxes and N leaching on the other hand. Via an evaluation of recent literature on the effects of these soil management strategies on SOC stock changes, MBC, MBN, GHG emissions, and nitrate leaching it identifies the most important knowledge gaps but also evaluates the main trade-offs and synergies related to soil C sequestration, GHG emissions, and N leaching. As such, this unique report should assist researchers to design experiments that allow to gain a better insight in the trade-offs and synergies. The report is a comprehensive basis to be used in other work packages (WP3, WP4) of the ΣOMMIT-project to design specific experiments and targeted measurements or simulations, also useful for EJP-SOIL and other similar projects.

2. Methods

This report was compiled via a collaboration between eight EJP SOIL partner institutes: EV-ILVO (Flanders, Belgium), CREA (Italy), CSIC (Spain), INRAE (France), IUNG-PIB (Poland), LUKE (Finland), NIBIO (Norway), and ULBF (Slovenia). In agreement with the Σ OMMIT consortium, the most important agricultural soil management strategies were identified for four soil management strategy categories: tillage management, cropping systems, water management, fertilization and OM inputs (Table 1). For the water management category, the selected strategies focused on irrigation techniques. However, despite relevant in some European regions, it was decided not to consider paddy soils and rice cultivation. The definitions of these soil management strategies are in line with the general EJP SOIL glossary and is included in the knowledge (gap) report excel template (vide infra). A knowledge gap is defined as insights that are not yet (fully) available, which can be caused by a lack of essential data.

Table 1: Most important soil management strategies in EU agriculture as considered by the Σ OMMIT consortium. These strategies are grouped per soil management strategy category (in bold).

Tillage Management	Cropping Systems	Water Management	Fertilization and OM inputs
-Inversion tillage -Non-inversion tillage -No tillage	-Monoculture -Crop rotation -Intercropping -Permanent crop -Agroforestry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Alley cropping ➤ Hedgerows / Shelterbelts ➤ Silvopasture 	-No irrigation -Drip irrigation -Flood/Furrow irrigation -Sprinkler irrigation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Center pivot irrigation ➤ Lateral move irrigation ➤ Solid-set sprinkler irrigation ➤ Hand move sprinkler irrigation ➤ Traveling gun sprinkler irrigation 	-Crop residues -Cover crop (Green manure / Mulch) -Livestock manure -Slurry -Compost -Biochar -Liming -Digestate -Sludge

The collection of relevant literature was performed by all partner institutes involved in Task 1 and Task 2 of work package two. The step-by-step plan is illustrated in Figure 1. Literature was collected from institutional and personal libraries of the partners and were screened for both in-house and externally performed research. In order to identify relevant and up-to-date knowledge and knowledge gaps, this report only includes literature published since 2010. In addition, the literature had to comply with a number of other selection criteria. Especially reviews and meta-analysis were included in the literature search. In the first instance, these were only included when describing the effect of the selected soil management strategies on the trade-offs and synergies between carbon sequestration and GHG emissions or nitrogen leaching. Since this specific type of literature was expected to be scarce, also literature that describes the effects on GHG emissions or nitrogen leaching or carbon sequestration or micro-organisms or a combination of these topics was included. Each of the latter topics was also called a focus. Original research papers were especially included when trade-offs or synergies between carbon sequestration and GHG emissions or nitrogen leaching were described. In case such papers were very scarce, relevant original papers describing the effects of soil management strategies on carbon sequestration, GHG emissions or nitrogen leaching were included. Effects were considered in both conventional and organic farming systems.

Further, only a limited number of land use types were considered (Table 2): arable land (including legumes), permanent crops (woody crops), pasture/grassland, fallows and heterogeneous agricultural

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

areas (e.g., annual crops associate with permanent crops). A final restriction was the geographical scope, since all selected literature had to be relevant for European agriculture. Therefore, a distinction was made between regional, national, EU and global literature items. A regional publication describes research performed in a specific region in a European country, or a region across the borders of some European countries. A national literature item only considers research from a specific country, while an EU literature item investigated effects for (parts of) Europe. Global narrative reviews and meta-analyses included at least one EU study of which the first author was affiliated to an European research institution.

Figure 1: General step-by-step plan that was used to collect literature, process literature, extract relevant information from literature and to compile this report.

Table 2: Land use types considered as important in Europe and used as a selection criteria during literature screening.

Land use types
Arable land (incl. legumes)
Permanent crops (woody crops)
Pasture/grassland
Fallows
Heterogeneous agricultural areas

All collected literature was stored in an online library in Teams and was assigned a structured name according to following code: First Author_year_soil management strategy category_focus_type of literature. Next, literature items were grouped according to the soil management strategy categories and relevant information was extracted and inserted in an online knowledge (gap) excel template. The template contained multiple automated dropdown menus and was constructed using a vocabulary based on the FAO, WRB/USDA, Agrovoc, Corine Land Cover standards. This excel template also included a description tab which provided the definitions of most dropdown menu items. These include land use, soil management strategies from all four categories. Besides this information, the template provides for each literature item a comprehensive summary of the treatments that were

studied, the main conclusion, the identified knowledge gaps and research recommendations but also the personal comments of the data entry person on the literature item. If extra literature was required, the search terms by which they were found, were represented in the excel-template. In total, 110 unique literature items were included: 31 reviews, 46 meta-analyses, 33 original papers. Since some literature items describe effects of several soil management strategy categories, the excel template in total comprises 144 input lines. A major part of the described effects considered Fertilization and OM input (82 input lines, 56,9%), while a similar number of effects were described for Tillage management (25 input lines, 17,4%) and Cropping systems (25 input lines, 17,4%). For Water management, an effect was identified only 12 times (8,3%) (Table 3). The most relevant literature items were then included in this report (Table 3).

Table 3: Number of literature items that describe the effects of a soil management strategy category on trade-offs, synergies, GHG emissions, nitrogen leaching, carbon sequestration or micro-organisms or a combination of these topics. Note that a single literature item can describe the effects of multiple soil management strategy categories and that it can be included more than once per category if it describes multiple soil management practices. Between brackets the number of the most relevant literature items that are included in this report can be found.

Soil management strategy Category	Number of literature items describing a soil management strategy
Tillage Management	25 (24)
Cropping Systems	25 (23)
Water management	12 (11)
Fertilization and OM inputs	82 (68)
TOTAL	144 (126)

The knowledge (gap) excel template served as the basis for this report. This report comprises one section per soil management strategy category (see section 3.1 – 3.4). For the soil management strategy category fertilization and OM inputs five subsections (3.4.1-3.4.5) were created. For each section and subsection, two tables were constructed. In a first table (example in Since subsequent reports of the Σ OMMIT-project will focus on the role of microbial communities and biomass on the trade-offs between C sequestration and non-CO₂ GHG emission and N leaching, the impact of soil management strategies on MBC and MBN is already considered in this report. In addition, also some soil management strategy categories may have an impact on the mineralization and respiration of SOC. For this, also the impacts on CO₂ emissions are described within this report.

Table 4) an overview is presented for each literature item of the effects of a soil management strategy category on the soil organic carbon change, microbial carbon (MBC) and nitrogen (MBN), N₂O and CO₂ and CH₄ emissions and N leaching. For each relevant literature item a qualitative evaluation of these effects was made and reported in this table. All effects are indicated by a color code: a green cell indicates a positive effect, a red cell a negative effect and a grey cell indicates a neutral effect. A positive effect for SOC, MBC and MBN change indicates an increase in the respective content, while a positive effect for a GHG emission and nitrogen leaching indicates a decrease of the emission or leaching. A negative effect indicates a decrease in SOC change, MBC or MBN and an increase for the GHG emissions. Since some literature items brought together the effects from different climatic zones, soil types, crops, the described effects depended on these specific conditions. As a result, more than one color can be introduced in the table for one literature item to describe the effect of a soil management strategy category on the parameter. When an effect was not assessed in a specific literature item, this is mentioned as N/A. In the bottom row, a qualitative summary is made of the general effects of the specific soil management strategy category on the previously described

parameters. The extraction of this general effect for each parameter was based on the overall evaluation of the effects as estimated by the different literature items included in the table which investigated this parameter. If the evaluation of the effects as indicated by the different literature items did not result in a distinct output (green/red/grey), a question mark was introduced. This question mark can indicate a) evidence is lacking and more research is therefore needed, b) different literature items reported contrasting results and more research is needed to get better insights into the specific effect, and c) information on the effect is lacking in most of the literature items (indicated by N/A) which did not allow to make a general conclusion.

Since subsequent reports of the ΣOMMIT-project will focus on the role of microbial communities and biomass on the trade-offs between C sequestration and non-CO₂ GHG emission and N leaching, the impact of soil management strategies on MBC and MBN is already considered in this report. In addition, also some soil management strategy categories may have an impact on the mineralization and respiration of SOC. For this, also the impacts on CO₂ emissions are described within this report.

Table 4: Example of the first table that is constructed for each section and subsection of chapter 3. For each literature item that describes the effect of a soil management strategy on the parameters mentioned in italic in the title row a new row is foreseen in which a color code indicates the impact compared to business as usual or other soil management strategies as indicated in the figure legends. A green cell indicates a positive effect, a red cell a negative effect and a grey cell indicates a neutral effect. For each literature item it is indicated in superscript if it concerns a meta-analysis (1), review (2) or an original paper (3). In the summary row an overview is given of the general effects of the specific soil management strategy category.

References	Publication level	<i>SOC change</i>	<i>MBC</i>	<i>MBN</i>	<i>N₂O emission mitigation</i>	<i>CO₂ emission mitigation</i>	<i>CH₄ emission mitigation</i>	<i>N leaching</i>
Example et al. (year) ³	Regional (EU)		N/A					N/A
SUMMARY								

Table legend:

1- Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

positive	negative	neutral
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In a second table that is foreseen in each section and subsection of Chapter 3, an overview of the knowledge gaps and research recommendations is provided. These were grouped per theme, resulting in 7 themes: the specific soil management strategy, pedoclimatic conditions, establishment of experiments, other soil management strategies, meta-analysis, modelling and other. For the cropping systems, an extra table is foreseen in which an overview and definition of the studied cropping systems is provided. The existing knowledge on the studied effects, the knowledge gaps and research recommendations are described in more detail in the sections and subsections of Chapter 3. Each of these (sub)sections ends with a concluding paragraph.

3. Soil Management Strategy Categories

3.1 Tillage Management

Tillage has historically been carried out to optimize soil conditions for germination, seedling establishment, and crop growth, as well as for mechanical destruction of weeds, crop residue management, fertilizer incorporation into the soil, etc. However, conventional tillage (intensive ploughing and harrowing with a total inversion of the soil) can increase vulnerability to soil erosion, soil compaction, and energy costs for the mechanical operations. Therefore, to mitigate some of these negative effects and to preserve SOC, less intensive tillage practices (also referred to as reduced or minimum or conservation tillage) and no-till (the absence of mechanical soil disturbance) have been promoted in recent decades.

As definitions of various tillage systems are not consistent in the literature, we use the following terminology: Tillage systems are grouped into “no-till” and “tillage”, which is further subgrouped into “non-inversion” and “inversion” (conventional ploughing) tillage. It is important to note that inversion tillage is still the most commonly practiced tillage system in the EU, so switching to less intensive tillage systems could have valuable potential for mitigating climate change. However, promotion of non-inversion tillage should be type specific, as also non-inversion tillage practices, such as deep chiseling, could be aggressive.

Effects of tillage management on SOC change

Reducing tillage intensity generally increases topsoil SOC content (Table 5), but the effect on the total (overall soil profile) SOC storage is controversial in literature. It must be acknowledged that the main effect of reduced tillage is a redistribution of SOC towards the soil surface. Therefore, field trial data included in reviews and meta-analyses need to be carefully examined to distinguish between a true increase in SOC stocks and a simple change in the vertical distribution of SOC concentration (Haddaway et al., 2017; Guenet et al., 2021). Among the papers selected for our report, there are only two studies with complete datasets that allow calculation of total SOC storage (Kraus et al. 2017; Tiefenbacher et al., 2021), while several studies reported the SOC storage in the upper 0-30 cm (Aguilera et al. 2013a; Dignac et al., 2017; Haddaway et al., 2017; Autret et al., 2019; Guenet et al., 2021; Payen et al., 2021). In contrast, many meta-studies do not even report the soil depth considered in their analyses (Table 5, see notes). Thus, the impact of tillage on SOC stock below plough layer, as well as impact of the pedo-climatic conditions on the SOC sequestration potential requires further research.

In some of the reviewed papers several other management practices with a potential impact on SOC were studied, such as organic matter amendments, fertilization, and irrigation. For example, Kraus et al. (2017) compared reduced tillage with conventional ploughing in interaction with two fertilization systems (cattle slurry alone (SL) versus cattle manure compost and slurry (MC)). The combined effect, reducing tillage intensity and additional application of manure compost (MC), showed the highest SOC stock increase after thirteen years (+8.1 Mg C ha⁻¹, 0-0.5 m). However, most studies investigated the effect of tillage as a stand-alone practice, which is far from representative for general agricultural practices. Therefore, important knowledge gaps exist regarding the combined effects of tillage and complementary practices on SOC.

Effects of tillage management on GHG emissions

N₂O emissions

An ongoing debate remains on how different tillage systems are influencing N₂O emissions. Since N₂O emissions are a product of a microbially guided process, it is influenced by several soil properties

altered through tillage, such as SOC and nutrient contents, water holding capacity, porosity, and soil structure as well as soil air-water conditions. Heterotrophic denitrification, as the main source of soil-borne N₂O emissions, is influenced by available soil carbon and anoxic conditions. Both parameters are usually increased as a result of reduced tillage intensity due to SOC accumulation. In addition, an increased nitrogen and water retention can be caused by improved water holding capacity, porosity, and hydrophilicity (Guenet et al., 2021). However, in the short term, no-till can promote higher soil density, resulting in a lower porosity and higher water content, creating favorable conditions for denitrification. In addition, an increased soil microbial biomass associated with reduced tillage intensity is supposed to be more related with N₂O emissions and less with CO₂ or CH₄ (Mangalassery et al., 2014). Similarly, Krauss et al. (2018) found that N₂O emissions are collinear with microbial biomass and SOC, and consequently higher emissions were observed under non-inversion (minimum tillage) than under inversion tillage (ploughing). However, this observation of higher N₂O emissions under reduced tillage intensity may differ for different soil management systems (fertilization, crop rotation,...). Tellez-Rio et al. (2015a) reported that there was no difference in annual cumulative N₂O emissions from a low N-input fallow-wheat rotation between no-till, non-inversion (minimum) tillage and conventional ploughing; while annual N₂O emissions from a cropping systems with legumes were higher under non-inversion (minimum) tillage in comparison to no-till and conventional ploughing (Tellez-Rio et al., 2015b).

Recent meta-analyses suggest that N₂O emissions are either unchanged or slightly reduced under no-till and reduced tillage in most cases (Mangalassery et al., 2014). As GHG emissions are influenced by soil type, local climate, weather conditions and duration of the experiment, it is difficult to draw a general conclusion which indicates that further research is required.

CO₂ emissions

In general, no-till is expected to produce lower CO₂ emissions (Abdalla et al., 2016). However, the results may strongly depend on local climate, SOM content, soil physicochemical properties, microbial composition, and crop rotation (Abdalla et al. 2016; Shakoor et al. 2021a). For example, Abdalla et al. (2016) found that the decrease in CO₂ emissions was more pronounced under no-till in dry climates, sandy soils with lower SOC content, and under crop rotation (as opposed to monocropping). In contrast, Shakoor et al. (2021a) found increased CO₂ emissions under no-till in rainfed areas due to higher microbial biomass in the topsoil.

CH₄ emissions

CH₄ emissions can be influenced by tillage practices (Huang et al., 2018). In general, no-till has no effect on CH₄ uptake, but it can reduce CH₄ emissions. The latter effect seems to decrease in the long-term duration of no-till and is also influenced by crop type and soil pH (Huang et al., 2018).

The bottom line is that the higher N₂O emission potential in no-till systems is offset by a lower potential for CO₂ and CH₄ emissions, depending on the geometry of the soil porous architecture (Mangalassery et al., 2014).

Effects of tillage management on nitrogen leaching

Few studies have simultaneously estimated N leaching and SOC stocks and/or GHG emissions under different tillage systems. One of the few studies found no differences in N leaching between conventional tillage and no-till (Autret et al., 2019). Moreover, Autret et al. (2019) found that N leaching was not related to N surplus. The results of Daryanto et al. (2017) suggest that changes in water flux between tillage systems do affect N leaching, and thus N loads to groundwater.

Conclusion

To conclude, reduced tillage intensity increases SOC content in the upper 30 cm of the soil, while the total SOC stocks in the soil profile remains to be examined. Further studies are also needed to investigate the underlying mechanisms of SOC stability.

In contrast, GHG emissions were influenced by the tillage system. Most studies confirm that soil bio-chemo-physical properties in addition to pedo-climatic conditions, and agricultural management practices (crop rotation, cover crops, fertilization, irrigation...) as well as the duration of the experiment are important factors influencing the validity of the results. More research is needed with different duration of experiments in different cropping conditions to explain the observed discrepancies. To better understand the trade-offs between SOC sequestration and GHG emissions more studies should consider both parameters in the same experiment on a longer temporal scale (Table 6).

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 5: The effect of reduced tillage intensity on SOC sequestration, GHG balances (CO₂ eq.), N₂O, CO₂, and CH₄, emissions, and N leaching losses. No-tillage and non-inversion tillage are compared to the conventional inversion tillage (ploughing).

References	Publication level	SOC change		GHG balances (CO ₂ eq)		N ₂ O emission mitigation		CO ₂ emission mitigation		CH ₄ emission mitigation		N leaching	Notes
Abdalla et al. (2016) ¹	Global			N/A		N/A				N/A		N/A	SOC for 0-30 cm depth
Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹	Global			N/A						N/A		N/A	SOC stocks for 0-30 cm depth
Debaeke et al. (2017) ²	Global			N/A		N/A				N/A		N/A	N/A
Daryanto et al. (2017) ₁	Global	N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A			N/A
Guenet et al. (2021) ²	Global							N/A		N/A		N/A	SOC stocks for 0-30 cm depth
Haddaway et al. (2017) ¹	Global			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	SOC stocks for 0-30 cm depth
Hénault et al. (2012) ²	Global			N/A				N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A
Huang et al. (2018) ¹	Global											N/A	N/A
Lee et al. (2019) ¹	Global			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A
Mei et al. (2018) ¹	Global			N/A				N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A
Morugán-Coronado et al. (2020) ¹	Global			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A
Payen et al. (2021) ¹	Global					N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	SOC stocks for 0-30 cm depth
Sanullah et al. (2020) ²	Global											N/A	N/A
Shakoor et al. (2021) ^{a1}	Global											N/A	N/A
Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²	Global			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	SOC stocks for 0-60 cm depth

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

van Kessel et al. (2013) ¹	Global	N/A		N/A				N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Lugato et al. (2018) ³	EU									N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sandén et al. (2018) ²	EU			N/A				N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Vazquez et al. (2019) ²	EU			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	SOC accounted for 0-10 cm depth
Autret et al. (2019) ²	Regional (in EU)									N/A			SOC stocks accounted for 0-30 cm depth
Dignac et al. (2017) ²	Regional (in EU)			N/A		N/A		N/A		N/A	N/A		SOC stocks accounted for 0-30 cm depth
Krauss et al. (2017) ³	National (EU)							N/A			N/A		SOC stocks accounted for 0-50 cm depth
Tellez-Rio et al. (2015a,b) ³	Regional (EU)			N/A				N/A				N/A	SOC accounted for 0-15 cm depth.
SUMMARY						?				?	?		SOC – can be generalized only for the topsoil.

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

no-tillage (zero-till) **non-inversion tillage** (minimum/ reduced tillage)

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 6: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on tillage (RT, NT and CON)

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
GHG emissions	-Lack of GHG balance in the long term, especially for N ₂ O;	- Calculation of GHG emissions in the long term; -Estimate precisely the impact of changes in agricultural practices on GHG fluxes;	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	-Emission factors for complex and different farming systems	- Emission factors should be derived from an entire crop rotation to better acknowledge the complexity of different (organic) farming systems;	Krauss et al. (2017) ³
Pedoclimatic conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The impact of the presence of a coarse fraction in soils when calculating SOC stock. This is currently an important source of error in SOC stock estimations; – Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors; – Estimations on changes in SOC are difficult to perform since full C input estimations are very scarce; – The effect of soil management strategies on SOC stock is misrepresented when only surface depths (average 23 cm) are considered; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -When studying the effect of soil management strategy, provide information on: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Coarse fraction 2. Bulk density data that allow SOC stock calculations - Consider all C inputs when investigating changes in SOC stocks after application of external OM; - Study SOC storage in deeper soils (deeper than 0.3m); 	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹
		-Reliable and precisely resolved data (soil parameters, land use patterns and practices) particularly at large spatial scale;	Dignac et al. (2017) ²
	- quantification of the potential of SOC sequestration options on a local to regional basis	-Focus on research that quantifies the potential of SOC sequestration options on a local to regional basis;	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	– Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors	- When studying the effect of soil management strategy, provide information on individual bulk density data across all treatments and depths;	Haddaway et al. (2017) ²
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of of microbes in soil structural development with an emphasis on their mechanisms - Nutrient uptake by plants under conservation system: conservation agriculture practices sustain the soil nutrients pools within the system but the mode, transportations and transformations, especially of N and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Investigate the the mode, transportations and transformations, especially of N and P in soil nutrient pools under no/minimum tillage conditions; – Extra research on the fate of pesticides under cover crop conditions; 	Sanauallah et al. (2020) ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	<p>P are poorly understood in no/minimum tillage conditions;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The fate of pesticides under cover crop conditions is not well-known 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The impact of tillage on SOC stocks in different layers including subsoil. -Interaction between soil tillage, nutrient accumulation and fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – When investigating the impact of tillage on SOC stocks in different soil layers it is recommended to use the equivalent soil mass approach. – When investigating the impact of soil tillage, differentiate between different types of tillage and tillage depth – Since reduced tillage practices can cause an accumulation of N, P, and K in the upper soil layer (0–20 cm), the combination of reduced tillage and reduced fertilization should be examined in detail. 	Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Trade-off effect in different European pedo-climatic zones 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Trade-off effect in European climatic zones should be further investigated 	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
Establishment of experiments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term effects of tillage: experiment length is usually short or medium term (average 8.7 years); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install long-term monitoring of experimental sites; 	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹ , Dignac et al. (2017) ²
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term effects of tillage -Effect of different/alternative conservation agriculture or organic managements systems varying in the nature and importance of legume residue returns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Install long-term monitoring of experimental sites; – Need to investigate other conservation agriculture or organic managements systems varying in the nature and importance of legume residue returns. This investigation can be done using experiments, modelling or both; 	Autret et al. (2019) ²
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Long term effects of tillage -variability separated by treatment, soil depth and other factors considered, including other farming practices such as different crop rotations or fertilizer rates; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Maintain experiments over 10 years and separate these experiments over time; – Reliable and precisely resolved data (sample size, measures of variable separated by: treatment, soil parameters, land use patterns and practices, long-term study data separated over time); – When installing new experiments, take into account sample sizes for true replicates. True replicates are those that occur at the same level as the factor of interest, e.g., if tillage treatments are applied to 	Haddaway et al. (2017) ² ,

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

		different fields, then true replicates must occur at the field scale; subplots are pseudoreplicates;	
	- Easily measurable indicators of soil N ₂ O emissions; - Insight in N ₂ O uptake by soils or N ₂ O peaks distant from fertilization events;	- Development of easily measurable indicators for N ₂ O emission potential; - A more general implementation of continuous emission measurements to investigate the N ₂ O fluxes over long periods (e.g., complete rotation);	Hénault et al (2012) ²
	-Impact of SOC sequestration practices on SOC stocks and GHG emissions in vineyards	-More exhaustive field experiments providing measurements of all necessary data to calculate changes in SOC stocks and GHG fluxes in vineyards under different SOC sequestration practices management are needed;	Payen et al. (2021) ¹
	-Impact of management practices on biological soil quality besides the impact on trade-offs	-Experiments should focus more on biological soil quality indicators as well as GHG emissions to enable better evaluation of trade-offs and mutual benefits of management practices.	Sandén et al. (2018) ²
	– Limited insight in GHG fluxes monitored for multiple seasons/years, existing studies only measured GHGs fluxes during the cropping and/or fallow seasons; – Insight in the GWP of single NT treatment and thus fluxes (CO ₂ , N ₂ O, CH ₄) induced by these treatments	– GHGs fluxes under CT and NT management practice should be measured during the whole year with specific time intervals, during the whole cropping season; – Studies should report the proper timing of NT practices, complete soil physiochemical properties like soil pH, bulk density, soil texture, water filled pore spaces, air temperature, climate zone, timing and amount of rainfall, N fertilizer rate and timing, flux type and unit, number of observations and control treatment, crop management practices in their future research studies – All three GHGs (CO ₂ , N ₂ O, CH ₄) fluxes under NT practice in a single study with the same treatments to calculate the GWP	Shakoor et al. (2021) ^{a1}
Other soil management strategies	-Synergetic effects of interactive practices e.g., agroforestry+biochar+covercrops etc. are poorly understood	-Focus on assessment of long term and interactive effects of soil building practices e.g., agroforestry+biochar+cover crops etc.;	Guenet et al. (2021) ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-Insights in combined effects of tillage and amendments, tillage and fertilizer on SOC	-Further investigation on combined effects of tillage and amendments, tillage, and fertilizer on SOC is required.	Haddaway et al. (2017) ²
Meta-analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<p>-When characterizing experiments, these meta-data should be described in detail to facilitate future analyses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study location (i.e., specific geographical location including coordinates) <p>Experimental name or field identifier (if a frequently studied long-term experiment or if multiple long-term experiments conducted at the same site).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study AND experimental timing (i.e., both the period of measurement and the period over which the management practice or experiment was in place). • Soil type (reported as clay/silt/sand or universally accepted soil texture classification). • Detailed description of the context, including cropping regimes, fertilizer rates, soil chemical and physical parameters. • Detailed description of the study design and experimental layout, including the type and level of randomization (i.e., how were plots randomly assigned, at what level of the experimental design was randomization applied [treatment, block, plot, subplot]) 	Haddaway et al. (2017) ²
Modelling	-The impact of soil management strategies on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers is largely unknown. The effect of soil management strategies on SOC stock is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered.	-C dynamics models should be applied to deeper soil layers because they are also impacted by agricultural practices and land-use patterns.	Dignac et al. (2017) ²
	-The understanding of interactions between the C and N cycle need to be improved.	-A better understanding of interactions between the C and N cycle is necessary to evaluate the benefits of different management practices aimed at increasing SOC storage and to predict the full GHG balance of each practice. Therefore, they should be better integrated in models.	Guenet et al. (2021) ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-Soil fluxes are still one of the most uncertain components in large-scale modelling.	-Improving biophysical modelling approaches, which can also handle other N sources than fertiliser input, is strongly recommended to have more realistic N ₂ O emission estimates for upscaling.	Krauss et al. (2017) ³
	-Impact of SOC sequestration practices on SOC stocks and GHG emissions in vineyards	-Further research is needed to quantify the change in SOC stocks in vineyards under different SOC sequestration practices, using modelling approaches	Payen et al. (2021) ¹
Other	-Mechanistic understanding and quantification of impact of different agricultural and forestry practices on SOC stock in different pedo-climatic conditions	- Importance of identifying, quantifying and classifying the different mechanisms according to the soil and climatic conditions in order to be able to model and predict soil organic C stocks under different agricultural and forestry practices. - Multidisciplinary interactions between researchers in the fields of soil science and ecology.	Dignac et al. (2017) ²

3.2 Cropping Systems

In the last decades, there has been a move towards more sustainable agriculture and cropping systems. Sustainable agriculture aims at establishing environmentally-friendly production by reducing the negative impacts of agricultural activities on all the components of the environment (Novak and Fiorelli, 2010). In this context, cropping systems (stockless arable or mixed crop-livestock) grounded on the achievement of agro-environmental protection, and socio-economic sustainability, can be considered as a well-developed form of sustainable farming. Commonly, cropping systems refer to all spatial (field to territorial levels) and temporal (growing season to years) aspects related to the combination of crop sequence with agricultural management practices (Debaeke et al., 2017). Crop sequence and crop cultivation are highly influenced by local pedo-climatic conditions.

In this section, different combinations of crop sequence and agricultural management practices have been considered in order to identify the most appropriate strategies and combinations for limiting the agro-environmental impacts of cropping systems by storing more organic carbon and increasing microbial C and N biomass (MBC and MBN) in agricultural soils or by reducing GHG emissions and nitrate leaching from croplands. Moreover, the impact of multiple trade-offs between cropping systems to deal with climate change adaptation and mitigation measures (i.e., increasing resilience and resource-use efficiency of the cropping systems) have been also identified and briefly discussed, in order to optimize the agro-environmental impacts of cropping systems at different scales (i.e., regional, National, European Union Countries, and global).

The most prominent cropping systems that have been considered in this section, ranging from monocropping to permanent crops and agroforestry are listed in Table 7. Monocropping represents the simplest type of crop sequence, where similar plants grow alongside each other from one season to the next, while permanent crops and agroforestry are the most complex systems, where multiplicity and heterogeneity of diverse plant types coexist within and between seasons.

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 7: List of cropping systems considered in the present overview. Terminology, description, and remarks of cropping systems have been adapted from Azam-Ali (2003) and Francis and Porter (2017).

Cropping System terms	Description	Remarks
1- Monocropping	The continuous growing of the same species on the same field, over a sequence of growing seasons	Risk of residual transfer of pests, diseases, and weeds from one season to the next
2- Crop rotation	On a same field and over time, crops are grown in rotation sequence one after the other with no overlapping phase	Requires long potential growing period
3- Intercropping	Multiple crops composed by two or more annual crops grown simultaneously on the same field within the same growing season	<u>Replacement intercrop</u> : each crop has the same seeding rate as the sole cropping <u>Additive intercrop</u> : additional crops of one or more species may be fitted into an existing population of sole crop
3a- Strip/row	Multiple rows of each crop alternating with other crops in field strips or different species arranged in alternating blocks of narrow rows	<u>Strip intercropping</u> : Strips are wide enough for some crops that internally act as a sole crop; strip borders show interspecific competition <u>Row intercropping</u> : Interspecific competition occurs between rows of different species
3b- Mixture	Crops of different species are randomly arranged spatially	These crops may be planted as replacement or additive intercrops to increase diversity, without affecting the yield of the main crop
4- Permanent cropping	Crops yielding harvests for several (usually more than five) consecutive years	
4a- Agroforestry	Land use system based on woody perennials (trees, shrubs, bamboos, palm trees, woody lianas) growing in association with annual or perennial herbaceous species and/or livestock:	Resource use efficient in both space and time. In such system, the woody component/s may provide more than one product and/or service
- Alley cropping (hedgerow intercropping)	Crops in a wide strip between lines of planted trees or shrubs	The woody component is always planted in rows but the spacing between rows depends on the species mix and topography.
- Hedgerows	Use of hedgerows as windbreak to shelter the crops	
- Silvo-pasture	Woody perennials growing on the same land as animals / livestock, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence.	
4b- Pastures	Any area available for grazing	
4c- Perennial non-woody crops	Crops often used as bioenergy crops such as <i>Mischantus</i>	
5- Land Use type		
5a- Arable land (incl. legumes)		
5b- Permanent woody crops	Trees or shrubs	
5c- Pasture/grassland (not grazed)	Grasslands not grazed by animals, no manure inputs or soil compaction	

Effects of cropping systems on SOC, MBC and MBN changes

Cropping systems and SOC dynamics are strictly linked. Some combined crop sequences and soil management practices can reduce SOC level (e.g., monocropping, crop residues removal, conventional agriculture) while others can enhance SOC storage (e.g., crop rotation, crop diversification, permanent crops, agroforestry, cover crops, conservation agriculture, and organic agriculture). Farmers can limit the organic C losses from soils through the adoption of beneficial SOC-preserving practices such as the integration of additional organic C to soils from the re-cycle of crop biomass (e.g., catch crops, agroforestry or deep rooting crops) also combined with external C sources (e.g., compost, manure, or recalcitrant biochar), as stated by Tiefenbacher et al. (2021).

Previous studies - conducted from regional to global level – have stated that many agronomic and conservation strategies including best crop diversification and soil management practices result in net gain in SOC stock as reported in Table 8. Woody crops in agroforestry systems are able to increase and stabilize SOC pools because they enhance C input, reduce C loss, and increase aggregate stability. In Kim et al. (2016), positive or neutral results regarding the relative contribution of agroforestry systems on SOC stock change were observed (ranging from 0.3 to 7.4 t C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). This behavior is attributed to different agroforestry management practices (i.e., tree-crop coexistence type and tree-crop rotation type), species used, densities of growing trees, or to differences in soil properties, land-use history, and climatic conditions. Long-term agroforestry systems with mixed plant species are more effective for SOC storage than systems with monocropping. Also, the inputs of C from roots and rhizodeposition may be of particular importance for SOC, since studies have shown that belowground plant inputs contribute to SOC through enhanced fine root production and rhizo-deposition (Kim et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2018).

Cropping systems based on crop rotation generally show positive effects on SOC stock change (Table 8). However, in a study covering a total of 251 European LTEs, Sandén et al. (2018) found that SOC content remained unchanged following crop rotation, with cycles ranging between 2 and 6 years. Some specific studies based on LTE experiments - comparing organic agriculture to conventional agriculture – observed higher SOC stocks in the topsoil under organic agriculture compared to conventional agriculture (Doltra et al., 2019; Hu et al., 2018). These findings confirmed the results obtained by Gattinger et al. (2012) who evaluated datasets from 74 studies that included data from pairwise field comparisons between organic agriculture and conventional agriculture. They found that soils under organic agriculture promoted SOC increase compared to conventional agriculture, mainly due to differences observed in crop rotations and total C inputs (i.e., the sum of external C inputs and crop residues). This is because cropping systems managed as organic agriculture are generally more oriented on mixed-systems (e.g., livestock and arable crops) - characterized by diversified rotations with higher percentage of legumes (grain or forage) in crop sequence - compared to conventional agriculture. In another meta-review, Leifeld and Fuhrer (2010) concluded that the higher SOC stock change under organic agriculture compared to conventional agriculture was mainly due to the higher application of organic fertilizer in organic systems instead of the practice itself. The effects of cropping systems managed under organic versus conventional agriculture on SOC changes has long been debated (Hu et al., 2018; Liefeld et al., 2012). Long-term experiments (LTEs) are a valuable resource that can provide a great opportunity for advancing efforts to reveal how different components of cropping systems and alternative management practices contribute to soil C inputs and to changes in SOC.

Within our selected studies, we found limited coverage (six out of nineteen studies) of specific cropping system effects on soil microbial biomass (i.e., MBC and MBN). Generally, the adoption of diversified crop rotations including N-fixing crops, deep-rooting crops, agroforestry, cover crops, bioenergy crops,

or grass buffer strips contributes to enhance MBC and MBN levels in agricultural soils. The meta-analysis and the review conducted at global level by McDaniel et al. (2014) and Sanullah et al. (2020), respectively, showed that crop rotation and diversification have a positive effect on soil microbial biomass compared to the monocropping systems. Similar findings were observed by Martyniuk et al. (2019) that conducted original studies at national level in EU. Regarding the cropping systems management, LTEs conducted at national level (Denmark) in EU by Hu et al. (2018) demonstrated positive impacts on soil MBC and MBN when cropping systems are managed under organic agriculture compared to conventional agriculture. These findings were confirmed by Doltra et al. (2019) in a study conducted at EU level. These differences in soil microbial activity may have affected turnover of the added organic matter resulting in different decomposition rate in organic versus conventional agriculture, which may also have influenced the changes in SOC stock.

Effects of cropping systems on GHG emissions

The literature review focused on assessing the contribution of cropping systems on N₂O, CO₂, and CH₄ emissions, showed positive (e.g., Goh et al., 2011, for N₂O and CO₂, and CH₄ emissions) negative (e.g., Kim and Kirschbaum, 2015 for N₂O emissions and CO₂ emissions) or neutral (e.g., Don et al. 2012, for N₂O and CH₄ emissions; Guenet et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2016, for N₂O emissions) impacts to the overall GHG emissions from agricultural soils. In their review carried out at global level, Sanullah et al. (2020) stated that under conventional agriculture, higher GHG emissions are observed compared to conservation agriculture.

In the review conducted by Hansen et al. (2019) at EU level, low N₂O emissions were observed during the growth of unfertilized legumes (grain legumes, grass–clover leys, green manure or cover crops) particularly when they grow in mixtures with non-legumes, because low soil mineral N concentration is associated with legume–rhizobium symbioses. Conversely, soil N₂O emission may enhance following termination or senescence of the legume crops due to re-active N released from dying roots and nodules (Rochette and Janzen, 2005).

In two recent syntheses (Guenet et al., 2021; Kim et al. 2016), minor differences in net N₂O emissions under agroforestry compared to adjacent agricultural lands were found. However, agroforestry can increase or decrease N₂O emissions. As reported in both reviews, an increase of N₂O emissions can be due to the greater N supply through N₂-fixing trees or to the incorporation of crop residues. In temperate regions where agroforestry systems are generally planted with non-legume trees, N₂O emissions are often reduced due to the presence of deep-rooted trees, that can reduce the amount of N available for nitrification and denitrification due to the lower soil moisture content under agroforestry compared to cropland because of the higher daily water consumption by trees.

Some studies reported no differences between conservation and conventional agricultural systems towards GHGs emissions (e.g., Bavin et al., 2009 and Fuß et al., 2011), while others observed an increase in N₂O emissions under conservation agriculture (e.g., Abdalla et al., 2013 and Ussiri et al., 2009) or a decrease compared to conventional agriculture (e.g., Almaraz et al., 2009 and Wang et al., 2011), depending on soil types and management practices.

In a comprehensive review on emissions from a large range of ecosystems (forestland, grassland, barren land, cropland and wetland), Oertel et al. (2016) highlighted that permanent pasture (sheep-grazing site) and permanent crops (e.g., willow short rotation crop, grass, miscanthus) showed significantly lower N₂O emission rates than annual cropping (e.g., winter-oat, fodder maize, and annual bioenergy crops) under CT and NT. Similarly, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions were reduced by rotation compared to monocropping. In this study, the relative contribution of N₂O emissions in terms of CO₂ equivalent, to the GHG emissions from these systems is relatively low. We might deduce from this that

a similar pattern can be observed within different cropping systems (agroforestry, cropland, grassland), and that CO₂ emissions are most likely the main contributor to GHG emissions also from our study systems.

Effects of cropping systems on nitrogen leaching

Regarding N losses by NO₃ leaching in soil, Hansen et al. (2019), stated that the risk of NO₃⁻ leaching outside the growing season are high in rotations with legumes (Table 8). However, Tonitto et al. (2006) concluded that NO₃⁻ leaching was reduced by 40% on average in legume-based systems compared to conventional fertiliser-based systems. Moreover, other authors (e.g., Neumann et al., 2011) emphasize that one of the most critical times for NO₃⁻ leaching in organic crop rotations occurs after soil incorporation of a grass-clover ley.

Debeake et al. (2017) reviewed studies at global level in the context of climate-smart agriculture and found that conservation agriculture could be a pillar of climate-smart agriculture in most parts of the world because it reduces soil NO₃ leaching. Moreover, they found that the introduction of cover crops in the rotation limits N losses by NO₃ leaching during the intercrop period (Table 8). For this purpose, both legumes (Guenet et al, 2021) and non-legumes Thapa et al., (2018) can be included in the crop rotation (see section 3.4.2). In a review conducted at EU level, Don et al. (2012) highlighted that permanent cropping reduces soil NO₃ leaching compared to arable crops. These findings were confirmed by Novak and Fiorelli (2010) who found that the introduction of permanent and catch crops in rotation limit soil N loss by NO₃ leaching. At regional level, Autret et al. (2019) carried out a study based on a 19-yr experiment in Northern France to evaluate alternative cropping systems to mitigate nitrogen losses and improve GHG balance. They found that conservation agriculture compared to organic agriculture increases N₂O losses by partially offsetting the very high SOC sequestration rate.

Conclusion

Based on this literature review, the potential effects of cropping systems based on different crop sequences and interacting management practices (e.g., tillage, fertilization, irrigation) on SOC stock change, MBC, MBN, GHG emissions, and nitrate leaching have been assessed and the main gaps in existing knowledge have been identified (Table 9).

Generally, the results presented in Table 108 show that cropping systems based on crop rotation with legumes, perennials, agroforestry, under conservation or organic management contribute to favor positive SOC stock change. An effect which may be influenced by other combined management practices (e.g., crop residues, cover crops, fertilization, and tillage) and environmental factors (pedoclimatic conditions). Nevertheless, Guenet et al. (2021) showed that cropping systems based on legumes that function as cover crops may induce trade-offs mainly related with N₂O emissions.

Agroforestry systems play a crucial role in increasing SOC stock and reducing net GHG emissions. At present, the amount of SOC stored by agroforestry systems cannot be accurately quantified because of the lack of a complete understanding of above- and below-ground biomass C storage in trees and/or shrubs. Thus, there is a need to improve the understanding of how the translocation of carbon and nutrients as well as belowground plant biomass of different cropping systems contributes to C inputs and retention in soils. Moreover, the C sequestration potential of relatively new management practices such as agroforestry is not conclusive because published data on long-term field experiments are lacking, and more specific studies are recommended.

Generally, agricultural soils are a sink for methane rather than a source. Consumption rates of atmospheric methane in soils are very low in European soils and climatic conditions. In certain conditions, soils can also be a sink for N₂O, but the factors regulating N₂O consumption are not yet well

investigated yet. Recently, minor differences in net N₂O emissions under agroforestry compared to adjacent agricultural lands were found (Guenet et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2016). However, no clear trend of change could be identified. For the relative contribution of conventional and conservation agriculture towards N₂O emissions contrasting results were observed (Table 8, Sanullah et al., 2020). The GHG mitigation potential of the investigated cropping systems was not reflected by their N surplus. All cropping systems improved the GHG balance, slightly for the low-input system, markedly for the conservation agriculture, and even more in the organic cropping system, which led to a negative GHG balance. Finally, cropping systems can both increase and decrease N losses by NO₃ leaching in soil, depending on the type of crop, crop sequence, agricultural management practices and pedoclimatic conditions.

A clear indication of trade-offs between N₂O emissions and SOC does not emerge from the selected studies. The impacts of cropping systems that increase diversity (intercropping, crop rotation) seem to be mainly positive in terms of SOC input to the soil as well as GHG emission mitigation. Further, an increased duration of the presence of the plant on the soil (perennial crops, agroforestry) seems to improve SOC input to the soil and reduce the emissions of GHG from croplands compared to annual crops.

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 8: The impact of cropping systems listed in Table 7 on changes in SOC stock, microbial C biomass (MBC), microbial N biomass (MBN), N₂O, CH₄, and CO₂ emissions, and N leaching. Crop rotation is compared to monocropping, agro-forestry to arable systems, and organic agriculture to conventional/conservation agriculture.

References*	Publication level#	SOC change	MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CH ₄ emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation	N leaching
Debaeke et al. (2017) ²	Global	MULT; GL; AGF and HEDG	N/A	N/A	LEG in ROT; GRASS BS; ORG	N/A	N/A	CC; CONS
Gattinger et al. (2012) ¹	Global	ORG	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Goh (2011) ²	Global	ORG	N/A	N/A	ORG	ORG	ORG	N/A
Guenet et al. (2021) ²	Global	ROT with LEG; CC; AGF	N/A	N/A	CC; SAS; RB LEG as CC AGF	N/A	CC; AGF	LEG as CC
Kim and Kirschbaum (2015) ²	Global	CG or CF FC or GC	N/A	N/A	CG or CF FC or GC	CG or CF	FC or GC	N/A
Kim et al. (2016) ²	Global	AGF	N/A	N/A	AGF	AGF	N/A	N/A
McDaniel et al. (2014) ¹	Global	ROT	ROT	ROT	N/A	N/A	ROT	N/A
Morugán - Coronado et al. (2020) ¹	Global	PER in alleys	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Oertel et al. (2016) ²	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	PAS and PER	N/A	ROT	N/A
Sanauallah et al. (2020) ²	Global	ROT and CC	ROT and DIV	ROT and DIV	CONS	N/A	ROT and CC	N/A
Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²	Global	ROT and DIV; CTC; NFC; and DRC; ORG; AGF and BEC	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	ROT and DIV; CTC; NFC; and DRC; ORG; AGF and BEC	N/A

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Thomas et al. (2013) ²	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	PER BEC		N/A	N/A	N/A
Don et al. (2012) ²	EU	PER	N/A	N/A	PER	PER	PER	PER	PER
Doltra et al. (2019) ²	EU	ORG	ORG	ORG	CC incorporated into the soil	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Hansen et al. (2019) ²	EU	N/A	N/A	N/A	LEG in organic ROT	N/A	N/A	LEG in organic ROT	LEG in organic ROT
Novak and Fiorelli (2010) ²	EU	PER; TLD; CG	N/A	N/A	PER in ROT; CTC	N/A	PER; TLD; CG	PER in ROT; CTC	PER in ROT; CTC
Sandén et al. (2018) ³	EU	ROT	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Hu et al. (2018) ³	National (in EU)	ORG	ORG	ORG	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Martyniuk et al. (2019) ³	National (in EU)	ROT with CC and GRASS without CC and GRASS	ROT with CC and GRASS without CC and GRASS	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Autret et al. (2019) ³	Regional (in EU)	CONV; LI; CONS, ORG; all without manure	N/A	N/A	CONS	ORG	ORG	N/A	CONV; LI; CONS, ORG; all without manure
SUMMARY	Global	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS	CONS; CC; CC incorporated into the soil; CG; CF	CONS; ORG; PER	ORG; AGF; CG; CF	ORG; PER, ROT	CC; LEG; ORG

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Abbreviations: **AC**: annual cropping; **AGF**: Agroforestry; **BEC**: bioenergy crops; **CC**: cover crops; **CF**: Land use change from cropland to forestry; **CG**: Land use change from cropland to grassland; **CL**: cropland; **CONS**: Conservation agriculture; **CONV**: Conventional agriculture; **CTC**: catch crops; **DIV**: crop diversification; **DRC**: deep-rooting crops; **FC**: Land use change from forestry to cropland; **GC**: Land use change from grassland to cropland; **GL**: grassland; **GRASS BS**: grass buffer strips; **HEDG**: Hedges; **LEG**: Legumes; **LI**: low-input; **MON**: monocropping; **MULT**: multiple cropping; **N/A**: Not assessed; **NFC**: N-fixing crops; **ORG**: organic agriculture; **PAS**: permanent pasture; **PER**: permanent cropping; **RB**: riparian buffers; **ROT**: crop rotation; **SAS**: silvo-arable systems; **TLD**: temporary leys of longer duration.

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 9: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on cropping systems

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Pedoclimatic conditions	- Effects of cropping systems managed under organic versus conventional agriculture on SOC changes	- Better investigate the soil type and climate under which the cropping systems are performed because the comparisons can be considerably influenced by the soil properties	Hu et al. (2018) ³
Establishment of experiments	-	In order to allow a better comparison of several studies, it would be useful to develop quality standards for: - site selection - flux and concentration units - long-term effects of intercropping and agroforestry not known - shallow sampling	Oertel et al. (2016) ² Morugán -Coronado et al. (2020) ¹ Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²
	- Effects of organic versus conventional agriculture on SOC changes - Impacts of various C input sources on the stabilization of SOC - Impacts of deep rooting crops is poorly studied	- Pay attention to the experimental design when comparing organic and conventional soil management practices since comparisons can be considerably influenced by the experimental design of the respective management - More detailed studies on measurements of C inputs from various sources and how the C inputs are degraded and contribute to stabilized SOC - Experiments with a focus on C inputs from roots and root exudates, to better assess the effects of cropping systems and crop management on SOC - Develop consolidated methods for improving the estimation of belowground C input	Hu et al. (2018) ³
	- Lack of knowledge on behaviour of N ₂ O emissions and NO ₃ leaching within organic arable crop rotations under field conditions.	- Develop locally adapted crop rotations and CC mixtures that concurrently reduce N ₂ O emissions and NO ₃ leaching - Optimise the use of crops and cover crops to enhance the synchrony of mineralisation with crop N uptake to reduce the long-term risks of NO ₃ leaching and N ₂ O emissions	Hansen et al. (2019) ²
	- Effects of increased temporal vs. spatial diversity	- Better investigate these beneficiary effects	McDaniel et al. (2014) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can SOC changes be positively affected by increasing diversity of cropping systems and how to implement this - There is limited information on the interaction between crop sequence and other soil management practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data from LTEs with different crop management and cropping systems may provide valuable insights on C inputs and on SOC changes - The potential interaction effects between crop sequence and other soil management practices such as tillage and fertilization that characterized the different cropping systems should be better investigated. Separate the effects of such practices to understand the influence of different cropping systems on SOC stock change, GHG emissions, and NO₃⁻ leaching 	McDaniel et al. (2014) ¹
Modelling	Process-based models fail to accurately simulate the impact of grass-clover leys on the turnover of N and C	Simulation models can be used to quantify N transformation and loss processes and to identify how different management practices affect N storage in SOM, and how short-term effects of crop residues and organic fertilisers affect N ₂ O emissions and NO ₃ ⁻ leaching	Hansen et al. (2019) ²
	No comprehensive process-based model to simulate crop rotations has been specifically developed for organic agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process-based crop models are potential useful tools to complement and upscale field observations under a range of soil and climatic conditions - The implementation of mineralization and turnover algorithms in other models has to be a priority 	Doltra et al. (2019) ²
Meta-analysis	/	/	/
Other:			
Underlying processes and impacts on the environment	- The relative contribution of increased SOM to microbial biomass, necromass; roots, and root exudates is poorly understood.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investigate the relative contribution of increased SOM to microbial biomass, necromass; roots, and root exudates -Develop and consolidate methods for improved estimation of belowground C inputs; investigate role of microbes in conservation agriculture 	McDaniel et al. (2014) ¹ Hu et al. (2018) ² Sanallah et al. (2020) ²
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific roles of microbes in soil structural development and mechanisms - Impacts of agricultural management practices and cropping systems on SOC sequestration and GHGs emissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Critically summarize cropping patterns with focus on sustaining the agro-ecosystems -Assess impacts of agricultural management practices and cropping systems on SOC sequestration and GHGs emissions 	Sanallah et al. (2020) ²

3.3 Water Management

Effects of water management on SOC change

The use of irrigation practices in agriculture, not only stimulates net primary production, but also the return of crop biomass to soil, which may lead to SOC build-up via greater carbon inputs. However, the increase of soil moisture induced by irrigation also favors the mineralization of SOC (Sapkota et al., 2020). The balance between these two processes will define if irrigation leads to soil C sequestration in a particular agroecosystem. A recent meta-analysis demonstrated that, on average, SOM mineralization by micro-organisms is outweighed by SOC accumulation via plant growth, mainly in arid and semi-arid regions showing an average increase of 5.9% in SOC with irrigation (Emde et al., 2021) (Table 10). However, increases in SOC stocks were only observed in sprinkler and drip irrigated soils, but not in flood- or furrow irrigated soils. The strongest SOC stock accumulations were noticed at the surface soil layer (0-10 cm) of semi-arid regions (Troost et al., 2013; Emde et al., 2021). Furthermore, SOC accumulation seemed to be dependent on the initial SOC concentration, with limited effects in soils with an initially high SOC content (Troost et al., 2013). In addition, the combination of irrigation with reduced tillage is assumed to stimulate SOC contents even stronger when compared to the combination with conventional tillage (Troost et al., 2013). Likewise, irrigation combined with N fertilization results in a stimulated SOC accumulation, mainly in soils with a sandy texture and low SOC content (Troost et al., 2013; Troost et al., 2016).

In order to better understand the effects of irrigation on SOC stock, the impact of climate, soil and initial SOC stocks need to be further assessed. Researchers should take into account the SOC storage in deeper soil layers to allow an accurate estimation of the effects of irrigation on SOC stocks. Researchers should also report data on soil bulk density and standard deviations in order to facilitate subsequent meta-studies. Further, changes in the water table and related effects on SOC stock processing should be investigated more in depth as well. In addition, it is important to study the interaction of irrigation with other agricultural practices on SOC stocks and to consider resource availability. Furthermore, there is scarce and disperse information on how water quality (use of saline water, wastewater) may affect SOC stocks in the long term. Also, the impact of water-saving irrigation strategies (i.e., deficit irrigation, subsoil irrigation) should be further investigated. Obtaining more insight in fundamental mechanisms is required as well. For example, the impact of irrigation on changes in soil texture and translocation of clay particles need to be investigated for in-depth understanding of the impact on SOC accumulation (Table 11). The formation of secondary carbonates in dry areas, which may lead to inorganic C sequestration has been seldom investigated and deserves further attention. Finally, given the low number of long-term studies included in reviews and meta-analyses, it is obvious that water management research would tremendously benefit from long term field trials.

Effects of water management on nitrogen leaching

The application of irrigation in agricultural areas may result in an increased risk on nitrate leaching (Quemada et al., 2013; Tiefenbacher et al., 2021) which in turn may lead to a reduced nitrogen availability for crops since water management interacts with the nitrogen use efficiency (Quemada et al., 2013). However, via the application of optimal management practices, nitrate leaching can be reduced considerably. In their meta-analysis, Quemada et al. (2013) described that when irrigation levels are adapted to the crop needs, a mean reduction of 80% of nitrate leaching can be obtained. In addition, they observed that also an improved irrigation schedule is important to control nitrate leaching and may potentially increase yields. These management practices are especially effective in furrow and flood irrigation systems, rather than in drip irrigated systems. Since the latter technique

was proven to allow a better control of nitrate leaching. Deficit irrigation helps to reduce nitrate leaching, but also results in a lower yield (Quemada et al., 2013).

By further improving the irrigation technologies, nitrate leaching can be further reduced. Because of the strong interaction with the fertilization level, both factors should be taken into account when studying leaching in irrigated agricultural zones. Furthermore, measurements of nitrate leaching should not be restricted to the growing season but conducted during a complete year.

Effects of water management on GHG emissions

The increased soil moisture level caused by irrigation usually stimulates soil-borne N₂O emissions (Table 10). This was shown by a number of studies comparing irrigated and rain-fed agricultural sites (Aguilera et al., 2013b; Trost et al., 2013; Cayuela et al., 2017), in which increases of 50 to 140% were reported (Trost et al., 2013). Stimulated N₂O emissions seemed to be strongly impacted by the availability of reactive nitrogen compounds (Trost et al., 2013; Kuang et al., 2021). However, N₂O emissions were also dependent on the soil type since lower emissions were observed in sandy soils (Trost et al., 2016; Kuang et al., 2021) and on the interaction with the cropping systems and fertilization. Furthermore, when expressed on yield-related basis, irrigation can result in lower yield-related N₂O emissions (Trost et al., 2016). Irrigation may also result in increased CO₂ emissions due to a stimulation of the soil microbial activity and increased plant biomass. In addition, an increment of the anaerobic conditions in soil may arise during irrigation, which can favor the emission of CH₄, especially in case of flood irrigation (Sapkota et al., 2020). This might be relevant mainly for paddy soils, but a meta-study focusing on upland soils is, at the moment, missing. In contrast, reduced irrigation may favor an reduction of the CH₄ emission (Sapkota et al., 2020).

Several studies investigated the effects of different irrigation techniques and found that (surface or subsurface) drip irrigation causes less N₂O emissions compared to sprinkler (Cayuela et al., 2017) or other conventional (furrow) irrigation techniques (Aguilera et al., 2013b). Water saving irrigation techniques seems to have a positive impact on N₂O emissions. Likewise, Kuang et al. (2021) suggested that drip irrigation can reduce N₂O emissions as compared to sprinkler or furrow irrigation. These techniques can contribute to a decrease in CO₂ emissions as well. Indeed, the regulated deficit irrigation technique not only resulted in an average decrease of N₂O emissions when compared to full irrigation, but also to reduced CO₂ emissions. However, since lower irrigation volumes are sometimes accompanied with a lower fertilization rate, the N₂O emission reduction may be attributed to an interactive effect of both irrigation and fertilization. Full irrigation was shown to result in a higher N₂O and CO₂ emission compared to regulated deficit irrigation applied via drip irrigation (Zornoza et al., 2018).

In order to better understand the impact of irrigation on soil-borne GHG emissions, more studies are required that include a non-irrigated control treatment. This may be challenging in some arid and semi-arid areas, where irrigation is a pre-requisite for crop survival. In these areas studies usually compare irrigated croplands with adjacent natural rain-fed lands. However, comparison of full irrigation with minimal deficit irrigation could be also used as a proxy. Next, studies should also include different irrigation techniques and irrigation rates, report water origin and quality (e.g., electrical conductivity, sodium adsorption ratio (SAR), residual sodium carbonates, DOC, etc.). An important limitation in current research is the lack of long-term experiments. Besides experiment duration, more attention should be paid to the effects of irrigation practices on CH₄ emissions, which should be especially investigated in irrigated upland soil systems. However, there is also a need for small-scale field or even laboratory experiments that allow to unravel the biogeochemical mechanisms of GHG production and diffusion through the soil matrix.

Another important factor is the interaction with other management practices such as fertilization (organic and synthetic). In addition, irrigation should be considered in a diversity of crops (including woody perennials) but also in organic farming systems. However, also the impact of soil type (including acid soil types), climate but also water quality should be further investigated. Finally, to fully understand the impact of irrigation on the GHG emission a full balance is recommended.

Conclusion

In general, the results presented in Table 10 demonstrate that irrigation contributes to an average increased SOC level. An effect which may however depend on the irrigation technique and environmental factors (climate, soil condition, crop and residue management). Nevertheless, irrigation induces trade-offs mainly with direct and indirect N₂O emissions (i.e., N₂O emissions and NO₃⁻ leaching). The effect on CH₄ in upland soils is still very uncertain as well as the trade-offs between C sequestration and GHG emissions. To date, studies that investigate the effect of irrigation on both C-sequestration and GHG emissions are very scarce (Troost et al., 2016; Zornoza et al., 2018). Such studies are very relevant and could provide better insights into the trade-offs between GHG emission/N leaching and C-sequestration. Another important gap in research that is very relevant to understand the impact of irrigation on N₂O emissions is related to the emissions associated to constructed (artificial) water bodies used for irrigation (Webb et al., 2021), where denitrification might be high and could, therefore, generate indirect N₂O emissions (Cayuela et al., 2017).

Table 10: The effect of irrigation on SOC, GHG emissions and N leaching losses compared to rainfed systems.

References	Publication level	SOC change		MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation	N leaching	CH ₄ emission mitigation
Aguilera et al. (2013b) ²	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A
Cayuela et al. (2017) ¹	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A
Emde et al. (2021) ¹	Global	Sprinkler	Drip	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Kuang et al. (2021) ¹	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A
Quemada et al. (2013) ¹	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A
Sapkota et al. (2020) ²	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A	Reduced irrigation vs. Non-reduced irrigation	Reduced irrigation vs. Non-reduced irrigation	N/A	Reduced irrigation vs. Non-reduced irrigation
Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²	Global			N/A	N/A		N/A		N/A

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Trost et al. (2013) ²	Global	Arid climate	Humid climate high SOC	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A
Trost et al. (2016) ³	Regional (in EU)			N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A
Zornoza et al. (2018) ³	Regional (in EU)	Reduced irrigation		N/A	N/A	Full irrigation vs. Deficit irrigation via drip irrigation	Full irrigation vs. Deficit irrigation via drip irrigation	N/A	N/A
Guardia (2016) ³	National (EU)	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
SUMMARY				N/A	N/A				?

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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Table 11: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles irrigation

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Irrigation	-Limited knowledge on differences in performance of irrigation methods -Long term effects of irrigations are insufficiently known	-Focus on studies comparing irrigation methods -Establishment of long-term field studies combining diversity of crops and irrigation methods	Aguilera et al. (2013b) ²
	- Lack of knowledge on the impact of irrigation on N ₂ O emissions, and on the impact of the amount and quality of water added - interaction with fertilization is poorly understood: organic and synthetic fertilizers	-Studies focusing on N ₂ O emissions as affected by water quantity and quality. - Study interaction effects with fertilization	Cayueta et al. (2017) ¹
	-Resource availability is poorly considered when	-Studies aiming at irrigation management practices to	Emde et al. (2021) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	investigating irrigation management aiming at increasing SOC stocks -Interactive effects with other management practices are poorly understood	increase SOC stocks must consider resource availability and the interactive effects of other management practices	
	-How can the irrigation system technology be an useful tool to reduce N-Leaching	-Improved irrigation system technology can provide an useful tool to reduce N-leaching	Quemada et al. (2013) ¹
	-Limited knowledge on differences in performance of irrigation methods	-Studies should investigate multiple irrigation strategies within a single field-based experiment	Sapkota et al. (2020) ²
	-The net effect of irrigation on GHG emissions is not known yet (a full balance is required). -The effect of irrigation on both C-sequestration and N ₂ O emissions is poorly investigated in specific experiments	-Effect of interaction between irrigation and management measures on N ₂ O emission and C-sequestration requires further research -Studies should investigate the effect of irrigation on both C-sequestration and N ₂ O emissions.	Trost et al. (2013) ²
	-A large-scale assessment of irrigation impact on GHG emissions	-More investigations on the effects of irrigation on GHG emissions for different soils, climates and agronomic management are necessary.	Trost et al. (2016) ³
	current IPCC EF model tends to overestimate N ₂ O production in response to NO ₃ loading across most artificial waters, particularly for farm dams		Webb et al. (2021) ²
Pedo-climatic conditions	- Understanding how SOC dynamics are affected by translocation of clay (and nutrients) in response to irrigation practices to enhance the efficacy of global efforts aimed at offsetting GHG emissions via SOC sequestration -The impact of irrigation on SOC stock cannot be calculated/estimated since data regarding irrigated agriculture are lacking: bulk density	-Examine changes in soil texture over time due to irrigation and at depth to better understand the role of soil texture in mediating irrigated agriculture-related changes in SOC, particularly on arid and semi-arid sites -Study SOC storage in deeper soils	Emde et al. (2021) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	(BD) and standard error or standard deviation are not reported - the effect of irrigation on SOC stock is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered.		
	-The effect of soil pH on N ₂ O emissions in acid soils	-Investigate the pH soil effect on N ₂ O emissions for acid soil	Kuang et al. (2021) ¹
	-The effect of irrigation and water table changes on SOC stocks	-Overall, the effects of irrigation and changes in the water table on SOC stocks and processing should be assessed further.	Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²
	-Lack of knowledge of the biogeochemical processes that drive GHG emissions	- small scale field or lab-based studies specifically probing potential biogeochemical mechanism are needed	Sapkota et al. (2020) ²
		there is a need to: (a) constrain the global abundance and distribution of artificial waters; (b) include artificial waters in the global N ₂ O budget, and (c) expand the study of N processing in artificial waters across a geographically diverse area to develop our biogeochemical understanding to the level that has been achieved for rivers and lakes.	Webb et al. (2021) ²
Establishment of experiments	-Short duration of experiments (usually less than 12 months), can lead to the underestimation of N ₂ O EF	-Install more long-term experiments	Aguilera et al. (2013b) ²
	-Lack of knowledge on long term effects of irrigation due to an average study duration of less than a year.	--Need of long-term field studies for a diversity of crops and irrigation methods	Cayuela et al. (2017) ¹
	-The effect of irrigation on SOC stock is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered. -Information regarding irrigated agricultural plots over longer duration (>15 years) is notably limited	-Take into account the effect of irrigation on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers -Install more long-term experiments	Emde et al. (2021) ¹
		-N leaching measurements should be conducted for a full	Quemada et al. (2013) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

		year, even if the growing period is shorter than this.	
	-Two years of deficit irrigation was not sufficient to detect significant differences in soil carbon quantity and quality.	-Longer term experiments are needed	Zornoza et al. (2018) ³
Other soil management strategies	-The interaction effects of irrigation with cropping systems on SOC stocks and GHG emissions are poorly investigated	-some types of cropping system need to be studied in greater depth, including rainfed, drip-irrigated, woody perennial and organic farming	Aguilera et al. (2013b) ²
	-Under what conditions can manure application increase soil C storage and crop productivity without increasing N ₂ O emissions	-Further studies are needed to determine the conditions under which manure application can increase soil C storage and crop productivity without increasing N ₂ O emissions.	Kuang et al. (2021) ¹
Meta-analysis	/	/	/
Modelling	/	/	/
Other	/	/	/

1- Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

3.4 Fertilization and Organic matter input

The following soil organic inputs and amendments have been focused on: crop residues (3.4.1), cover crop (3.4.2), livestock manure, slurry, and compost (3.4.3), biochar (3.4.4) and liming (3.4.5).

3.4.1 Crop Residues

Effects of crop residues on SOC change

A synthesis of 9 meta-analyses on the effect of crop residue incorporation on SOC changes showed a range of responses between 3 to 18% compared to crop residue removal (Bolinder et al., 2020), and European meta-analysis and long-term experiment about 6-7% (Lehtinen et al., 2014; Sandén et al., 2018). However, since the incorporation of crop residues into soils relates to tillage, this physical disruption of the soil surface might pose a risk for the SOC stock (Tiefenbacher et al., 2021).

The SOC content increased significantly with an increasing straw addition rate and straw C input rate (Xia et al., 2018). The impact on SOC is generally expected to be greater for grain-maize because the potential aboveground crop residues represent approximately twice the amount that of small-grain cereals (Bolinder et al., 2020). The impact is greater with a straw C/N ratio larger than 30 (e.g., cereal straw), compared to C/N ratio <30 (e.g., legume straw, Xia et al., 2018). The effect of straw return on SOC content was similar for different mineral N fertilization rates and application methods (surface application vs. incorporated) (Xia et al., 2018). Furthermore, the increase in nutrients availability following straw return was associated also with an increase in microbial biomass (Xia et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Siedt et al., 2021).

Experiment duration is highly variable across the studies, resulting in irregular conclusions for the effect of time on changes in SOC (Bolinder et al., 2020). Xia et al. (2018) concluded that experiments with a duration of more 4 years resulted in significantly higher C sequestration than short-term experiments, while other authors stressed the importance of experiments >20 years. Meta-analyses also showed inconsistent results for relationships between the changes in SOC due to residue incorporation and soil texture or climate, indicating a knowledge gap on the impact of pedo-climatic factors (Bolinder et al., 2020).

Effects of crop residues on nitrogen leaching

Global meta-analysis by Wang et al. (2018) clearly demonstrated that crop residue return (incorporation and mulching) resulted in a decreased N leaching (-9.1%) in upland fields (mainly with corn and wheat). However, meta-analysis by Xia et al. (2018) showed variable results: N leaching were significantly reduced in experiments fertilized with N rates < 160 kg/ha, or having clay content < 20%, or located in warm temperate climates, otherwise no significant changes in N leaching losses were observed. Other parameters, such as soil properties (soil texture), straw quality (straw C/N ratio) and quantity (straw N input rate), also strongly impact soil N transformations and N losses (Xia et al. 2018).

Xia et al. (2018) stressed clear synergy between SOC sequestration and N leaching reduction. However, there is lack of meta-analyses and reviews that summarize European studies on N leaching losses reduction due to residue return. In addition, the impact of pedo-climatic factors was not properly addressed in the previous research.

Effects of crop residues on GHG emissions

Straw C/N ratio was the main factor determining the variability of the N₂O emission response after residue addition, as indicated by two global meta-analyses (Chen et al., 2013; Xia et al., 2018). Crop residue amendment generated significantly stimulating effects on soil N₂O emissions when C/N ratios

were < 45, slightly stimulating effects for C/N ratios of 45–100, and slightly reducing effects for C/N ratios >100 (Chen et al., 2013). However, recent meta-analysis set the different thresholds of C/N ratio and their impact on N₂O emissions (Xia et al., 2018). The largest increase in N₂O emissions occurred when returning straw with a C/N ratio <30 (e.g., legume straws), whereas applying straw to soils with a larger straw C/N ratio (>30; e.g., cereal straws) did not stimulate N₂O emissions, or even significantly reduce them (C/N ratio > 60). Both meta-analyses agreed that N₂O emissions depended on straw type: wheat straw reduced emissions, while corn, bean, and particularly green manure and vegetables increased N₂O emissions. However, if meta-analyses, reviews and studies did not take into account straw C/N ratios, they reported a constant increase of N₂O emissions by 17% (Wang et al., 2018) or by 62% (Sandén et al., 2018), or 12 times higher (Lehtinen et al., 2014;) due to straw return. Chen et al. (2013) concluded that it is necessary to connect the quality and quantity of crop residues with soil properties for predicting soil N₂O emission. Also, the impacts of climatic factors on N₂O losses need to be studied, particularly, for cool temperate climate (Wang et al., 2018; Xia et al., 2018).

Conclusion

To summarize, although the effect of straw return on SOC increase was well studied globally as well in Europe, outcomes for N₂O emissions are controversial (Table 12), depending on quality and quantity of straw. Nitrogen leaching losses under straw return was less studied, and there is no European synthesis on this topic (Table 12). The impact of pedo-climatic factors is still poorly understood. The quality of meta-analysis needs to be improved, since problem with non-independence of effect sizes and unweighted procedure, which were common for the meta-analyses on straw return, may cause overestimation of results (Table 13).

Table 12: The effect of crop residue returns on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), and GHG emissions and N leaching losses compared to residues removal.

References	Publication level	Application method	SOC change	MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation	N leaching
Bolinder et al. (2020) ²	Global	I	positive	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Chen et al. (2013) ¹	Global	-	N/A	N/A	N/A	positive, negative, neutral	N/A	N/A
Siedt et al. (2021) ²	Global	I	positive	positive	positive	N/A	N/A	positive
Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²	Global	I	positive	N/A	N/A	negative	N/A	N/A
Wang et al. (2018) ¹	Global	I, S	N/A	N/A	positive	negative	N/A	positive
Xia et al. (2018) ¹	Global	I, S	positive	positive	positive	positive, negative, neutral	N/A	positive, neutral
Lehtinen et al. (2014) ¹	EU	I	positive	N/A	N/A	negative	negative	N/A
Sandén et al. (2018) ³	EU	I	positive	N/A	N/A	negative	neutral	N/A
SUMMARY		I, S	positive	positive	positive	positive, negative, neutral	?	positive

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

I-Incorporation; S-surface application

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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Table 13: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on residues returns (incorporation or surface application)

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Residues	In many meta-analyses and reviews the impact of residue C/N ratio on N ₂ O emission was not studied.	Residue C/N ratio needs to be taken into account, since it is one of the main driving factors impacting N ₂ O emissions.	Comment by Elena Valkama
Pedoclimatic conditions	Inconsistent results for relationships between the changes in SOC due to residue incorporation and soil texture or climate	The impact of pedoclimatic conditions need to be studied more in depth.	Bolinder et al. (2020) ²
	It is a necessity to connect the quality and quantity of crop residues with soil properties for predicting soil N ₂ O emission.	- More work needs to be done regarding residue effects on soil N ₂ O emissions for sandy soils and under more anaerobic conditions. -Soil properties need to be taken into account, to gain an improved understanding on crop residue factors driving N ₂ O emissions in agricultural soils.	Chen et al. (2013) ¹
	The impacts of soil properties and the impacts of climatic factors on N ₂ O and N leaching losses are poorly studied.		Wang et al. (2018) ¹
	Limited understanding of N ₂ O emissions and N leaching losses in cool temperate climate.		Xia et al. (2018) ¹
Establishment of experiments	Inconsistent conclusions for the effect of time on changes in SOC.		Bolinder et al. (2020) ²

	Insights from long-term experiments studying both SOC concentrations and GHG emissions are lacking.	More long-term field studies are needed to better assess the CO ₂ and N ₂ O emissions following crop residue incorporation, specifically from the same studies in which SOC is measured.	Lehtinen et al. (2014) ¹
	.	Perform more field experiments since constant laboratory conditions are not suitable, because many important aspects are masked	Siedt et al. (2021) ²
Other soil management strategies	Insufficient insights in the N rate and fraction of mineral N fertilizer, that is lost as N ₂ O or N leaching in different soils, which receive the application of straw with different C/N ratios.	It is important to monitor the fraction of mineral N fertilizer lost.	Xia et al. (2018) ¹
	Since the incorporation of crop residues into soils relates to tillage, this physical disruption of the soil surface might pose a risk for the SOC stock.	Investigate the interactive effect of the contribution of crop residues to the soil OM pool and the impact of its incorporation and thus soil disruption on the SOC stock evolution.	Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²
Meta-analysis	Performing meta-analysis to obtain new insights is hard since in many articles standard deviations were not reported, the meta-analyses by Chen et al (2013), Lehtinen et al. (2014), Wang et al. (2018), Xia et al. (2018) were not weighted by inverse variance.	Meta-analysis must account for unequal precision in the magnitude of the effect among studies by weighting each study's effect size by the inverse of its variance.	Comments by Elena Valkama
	Difficult to fully rely on results of meta-analyses to obtain new insights since	Effect sizes should be independent.	

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	there were also problems with non-independence of effect sizes. Therefore, the results may be overestimated.		
Other	The variation between individual sites in terms of SOC changes is large and the underlying mechanisms for these differences are not well known yet.	Since the variation between individual sites in terms of SOC changes is large, the underlying mechanisms for these differences should be investigated in future research.	Bolinder at al. (2020) ²

1- Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

3.4.2 Cover crop (Green manure)

Effects of cover crops on SOC change

Numerous global meta-analyses demonstrated that both non-legume and legume cover crops (CC) increased SOC stock by about 10-15% in the topsoil and favored microbial biomass carbon (MBC) and nitrogen (MBN) by about 40-50% compared to bare fallow (Table 14). However, meta-analysis by Jian et al. (2020) showed the positive effect on SOC due to legume CC only, but not non-legume CC. In addition, three European long-term experiments failed to prove the positive effect of CC on SOC (Sandén et al., 2018).

There are several constraints bringing uncertainty in SOC stock estimation, such as lack of data for subsurface layers (>30 cm), using pedotransfer functions instead of measurements of bulk density, non-accounting for the coarse particle fraction, and the lack of data on experiments longer than 10 years (Table 15). Therefore, it was recommended to maintain long-term experiments, to report soil bulk density to estimate SOC stock, to collect soil samples from subsurface, and to study the impact of soil characteristics, such as particle size, and species-specific CC effects on SOC.

Effects of cover crops on nitrogen leaching

Global meta-analyses clearly indicated differences between non-legume and legume CC in terms of N leaching reduction (Table 14). Guenet et al. (2021) carried out a specific review on the interactions between soil C and N dynamics and highlighted the importance of using legumes as cover crops to reduce soil NO₃ leaching. As observed by Thapa et al. (2018) the extensive use of legumes as cover crops can reduce NO₃ leaching by about 56% on average. Therefore, replacing a fallow with a non-legume cover crop reduced N leaching by about 50%, while using a legume did not have any effect on N leaching (Quemada et al., 2013; Thapa et al., 2018; Shackelford et al., 2019). Similarly, a European meta-analysis of 35 studies conducted in Denmark, Sweden, Finland and Norway over the past four decades showed that non-legume cover crops, mainly ryegrass species, undersown to spring cereals, reduced N leaching loss by 50% (Valkama et al., 2015). However, the effect of legume or mixed cover crops on N leaching losses in the Nordic countries have not been studied yet. A European review stressed that continued use of CC had the proven ability to reduce N leaching also from organic arable crop rotations, and a mixture of legumes and non-legumes was as sufficient as sole non-legumes but had a better impact on soil fertility than non-legumes (Hansen et al., 2018).

Globally, there is lack of data on long-term experiments, specific climate, such as dry cool and dry warm zones with annual precipitation ≤500 mm, data accounting for spatial variability of nitrate fluxes, and data on combination of different management practices, such as CC and no-tillage (Table 15). Thus, there is a need to conduct measurements for a full year and to maintain experiments over 5 years, to use multiple ceramic cup lysimeters to capture spatial variability of nitrate-N leaching over small areas. Combination of management practices, such as CC and tillage, fertilization, irrigation water must be studied in the future. Within-study variability (SD, SE, CV, or LSD) on nitrate-N leaching need to be reported to allow quantitative data analysis.

Effects of cover crops on GHG emissions

There is a clear difference between non-legume and legume CC in terms of their effect on N₂O emissions: legumes typically resulted in higher N₂O emission, while non-legume and mixed CC had either a neutral effect or reduced the emission (Table 14). In three European long-term experiments, N₂O emissions were significantly increased by 65% due to cover crops and green manure (Sandén et

al., 2018). A simulation model predicted that the introduction of N-fixing cover crops in Europe allowed higher C accumulation over the initial 20 years, but this gain was progressively offset by higher N₂O emissions over time. Furthermore, by 2060, around half of the sites became a net source of greenhouse gases (Lugato et al., 2018). One of the key points controlling CC effect on N₂O emissions is the frequency of leguminous crops integration in the crop rotation (Guenet et al., 2021). Many factors influence the magnitude of N₂O emissions, such as the C/N ratio of cover crop residues, their rate of decomposition, the extra inputs of fertilizer N applied to cover crops, whether the residues are ploughed or left to decay on the soil surface (Guenet et al., 2021). In contrast, all types of CC resulted in stimulated CO₂ emissions as demonstrated by meta-analyses, although the magnitude of their impacts was not consistent across studies, and varied from 15% (Shackelford et al., 2019) to 35% (Muhammed et al., 2019) compared to bare fallow.

There is a need to fill in knowledge gaps on the influence of CC residue quality and quantity on CO₂ and N₂O emissions (Muhammad et al., 2019), and on the impact of weather conditions impact on N₂O dynamics (Basche et al., 2014). Measurements of N₂O emissions over the entire year are required to determine the net effect of cover crops on N₂O (Basche et al., 2014).

Conclusion

In conclusion, based on the results of numerous global meta-analyses, reviews, long-term experiments and simulation models, trade-offs and synergies mostly depend on the type of CC and GHG. For non-legume CC, trade-offs between SOC increase and GHG emissions were demonstrated for CO₂, but not N₂O. A clear synergy was reported between SOC increase and N leaching reduction of 50% on average, both globally as for some regions in EU. For legume CC, positive effects on SOC were accompanied by stimulated GHG emissions but no N leaching reduction. However, there is no meta-analysis that summarizes studies on the effects of cover crops on SOC, N₂O emissions and N leaching losses across Europe, which reveals a knowledge gap need to be filled in.

Table 14: The effect of non-legume and legume cover crops on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and - Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N₂O and CO₂, and N leaching losses compared to no cover crops.

References	Publication level	SOC change		MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation		CO ₂ emission mitigation		N leaching		
Abdalla et al. (2019) ¹	Global			N/A	N/A			N/A				
Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹	Global			N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		N/A		
Basche et al. (2014) ¹	Global	N/A		N/A	N/A			N/A				
Jian et al. (2020) ¹	Global			N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		N/A		
Muhammad et al. (2019;2021) ¹	Global											N/A
Poepplau and Don (2015) ¹	Global			N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		N/A		

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Quemada et al. (2013) ¹	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A				
Shackelford et al. (2019) ¹	Global					N/A				
Thapa et al. (2018) ¹	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A				
Hansen et al. (2019) ²	EU	N/A	N/A	N/A				N/A		
								or+		
Lugato et al. (2018) ³	EU	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A	
Sandén et al. (2018) ³	EU			N/A	N/A			N/A	N/A	
Valkama et al. (2015) ¹	Regional (in EU)	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		
SUMMARY										

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

legume non-legume

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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Table 15: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on cover crops (CC)

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Cover crops	-The influence of CC residue quality and quantity on CO ₂ and N ₂ O emissions -Species-specific CC effects on SOC		Muhammad et al. (2019) ¹ Poeplau and Don (2015) ¹
	-Estimations on changes in SOC are difficult to perform since full C input estimations are very scarce.	-CC need to be adopted to specific soil, management and regional climatic conditions which requires further research.	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹ Abdalla et al. (2019) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-The effect of legume or mixed cover crops on N leaching losses in Nordic countries	-Perform measurements of N ₂ O emissions in field experiments with CC undersown with spring cereals.	Valkama et al. (2015) ¹
Pedoclimatic conditions	--Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors (e.g. soil bulk density).	--When studying the effect of a soil management strategy, provide information on soil bulk density to estimate SOC stock	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹
	- Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors. Calculations via pedotransfer functions bring uncertainty - over- or underestimation of SOC stocks.	-Soil samples from subsurface must be collected and investigated as well	Jian et al. (2020) ¹
	-The impact of the presence of a coarse fraction in soils when calculating SOC stock. This is currently an important source of error in SOC stock estimations.	-Study the impact of soil characteristics, such as particle size, on CO ₂ emissions due to CC.	Muhammad et al. (2019) ¹
	-The impact of a soil management strategies on SOC stocks is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered. There is currently a lack of data on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers.	-Take into account the effect of soil management strategies on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers	Poeplau and Don (2015) ¹
	-Impact of soil depth, stone content and SOC on the reduction of N leaching losses due to CC		Quemada et al. (2013) ¹
	-Lack of insights in N leaching in dry cool and dry warm zones (annual precipitation ≤500 mm)	-Perform N leaching experiments in dry cool and dry warm zones (annual precipitation ≤500 mm) -N leaching measurements should be conducted for a full year	Abdalla et al. (2019) ¹ Quemada et al. (2013) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-Weather impact on N ₂ O dynamics	-N ₂ O measurements over years	Basche et al. (2014) ¹
Establishment of experiments	-Effects on long term are not well studied yet.	-Maintain experiments over 5 years	Abdalla et al. (2019) ¹ Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹ Jian et al. (2020) ¹ Poeplau and Don (2015) ¹
	-A high degree of spatial variability for nitrate fluxes exists	-Using multiple ceramic cup lysimeters to capture spatial variability of nitrate-N leaching over small areas.	Thapa et al. (2018) ¹
	-Existing monitoring measurement systems and available data sets do not allow for robust estimations of N ₂ O emissions and conclusions on the possible trade-off between N ₂ O emissions and management practices that stimulate C sequestration		Lugato et al. (2018) ³
Other soil management strategies	-The impact of conservation tillage on N leaching is not well studied yet. Mostly conventional tillage (80%) vs. conservation tillage (20%) for N leaching dataset		Abdalla et al. (2019) ¹
	- Impact of the combination of management practices (cover crops, tillage, fertilization, irrigation)	-Focus on other management practices in combination with cover crops	Shackelford et al. (2019) ¹ Valkama et al. (2015) ¹
	- Insufficient knowledge on N ₂ O emissions and NO ₃ leaching within organic arable crop rotations	Perform experiments on N ₂ O emissions and NO ₃ leaching within organic arable crop rotations to create robust datasets	Hansen et al. (2019) ²
Meta-analysis	-Within-study variability (SD, SE, CV, or LSD) to allow quantitative data analysis	Some measures of within-study variability should be reported to allow quantitative data analysis	Thapa et al. (2018) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Modelling	-Lack of understanding of losses of C and N from above ground tissues and rhizodeposition which makes that no field-scale model includes all C and N turnover processes.	-Simulation models can be used to quantify N transformation and loss processes.	Hansen et al. (2019) ²
	-More insights in soil fluxes are require since these are still one of the most uncertain components in large-scale modelling	-A better integration between management intervention and biogeochemical C and N cycles should be transferred to Earth system models	Lugato et al. (2018) ³
Other			

1- Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

3.4.3 Livestock manure, slurry and compost

Effects of livestock manure, slurry and compost on SOC, MBC and MBN changes

SOC change

The application of animal manure, slurry and composts in general results in an increased soil organic carbon (SOC) content compared to inorganic fertilizers or no fertilization (Maillard et al., 2014, Shakoob et al., 2021b; Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). The rate of SOC increase depends on the properties of the OM input: application rate, C concentration, C input, animal species, management system: liquid or solid storage (Maillard et al., 2014). The most used among organic amendments is manure. Sandén et al. (2018) compared 251 European long-term experiments (LTEs) and observed that farmyard manure increased SOC contents by 21% on average. Gross et al. (2021) analyzed SOC change in many aspects, e.g., application of manure from different animal species, different climate regions, different soil textures and different soil pH. They observed a significant SOC increase of 35 % on average. Since manure is rich in organic matter and is a direct input of organic carbon into soil, this positive effect which is independent of pedoclimatic conditions and animal species could be expected (Gross et al., 2021).

SOC increase tends to be higher with compost amendment than with raw manure amendment, which is due presence of more stabilized forms of carbon (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Luo et al., 2018; Sandén et al., 2018). However, composts vary in feedstock and degree of decomposition which results in variable carbon sequestration potentials (Siedt et al., 2021). According to Tiefenbacher et al. (2021), the carbon sequestration potential of compost is $714 \pm 404 \text{ kg C ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$.

Liquid organic materials, such as slurries, are highly mineralized and characterized by a very low content of easily decomposable C. As a consequence, slurries demonstrate to have the lowest performance regarding SOC increase compared to other organic matter inputs (Aguilera et al., 2013a). However, their impact on SOC is still positive or neutral (positive but not significant) (Aguilera et al., 2013a; Sandén et al., 2018; Maillard et al., 2014). Sandén et al. (2018) report a SOC increase of 19% with slurry amendment. Nevertheless, slurries have not been thoroughly studied or compared with solid manure so far and thus more research is required (Maillard et al., 2014).

In summary, OM inputs increase SOC in almost all cases (Table 16). Non-significant (neutral) effects were observed in one meta-analysis studying slurry (Aguilera et al., 2013a) in comparison with different animal species manures. A meta-analysis comparing different animal species manures suggests that a positive impact on SOC might not be typical for all of them. There is only a limited number of studies on the comparison of different animal species manures so far, thus more attention is needed in future (Maillard et al., 2014). Data are highly variable and dependent on site-specific conditions e. g. manure or slurry storage conditions, fertilization methods and application rates, crop rotation and crop residue management. An additional knowledge gap on SOC change in agricultural systems is the low number of experiments focusing on permanent crops, as findings from Payen et al. (2021) suggest, that there is potential to increase SOC stocks in e.g., viticultural soils.

Microbial biomass carbon and microbial biomass nitrogen

Microbial biomass carbon (MBC) and microbial biomass nitrogen (MBN) were addressed in several research papers (Table 16). In all studies, the impact of OM inputs is positive on both MBC and MBN, regardless of the type of OM input (D'Hose et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2018; Sandén et al., 2018; Martyniuk et al., 2019). A meta-analysis of European long-term field experiments including manure, slurry and compost amendments compared to mineral fertilization reveals an increase for MBC of 25-31 %

(D'Hose et al., 2018). Luo et al. (2018) report an increase for MBC of 51 % and for MBN of 24 % in soils amended with farmyard manure and compost compared to mineral fertilization.

Effects of livestock manure, slurry and compost on nitrogen leaching

The addition of organic amendments plays a positive role in climate change mitigation by soil carbon sequestration. The size of which is dependent on their type, the rates, and the frequency of application. Repeated application of composted materials increases soil organic nitrogen content by up to 90%, storing it for mineralization in future cropping seasons, as most of the nutrients available from the feedstock are bound in organic forms during composting. Therefore, only about 5% to 15% of N is available in mature compost during the first year after application. Due to the reduced availability of N-forms in compost, it is often reported that nitrate leaching to groundwater after compost amendment is less than or equal to the situation of mineral fertilizer application (Diacono and Montemurro, 2010; Siedt et al., 2021). In summary, organic matter stability in the organic amendments determines the dynamics of mineral N release to crops and potential leaching to groundwater (Chalhoub et al., 2013).

Effects of livestock manure, slurry and compost on GHG emissions

N₂O emission

A meta-analysis conducted by Zhou et al. (2017) demonstrates that manure application (liquid and solid; raw and pre-treated) significantly increased soil N₂O emissions by 32,7 % on average compared to application of synthetic N fertilizer alone. A comparison of different animal species manure in the same study indicates variations, which are most likely a consequence of different manure compositions (Bell et al., 2016). N₂O emissions due to cattle manure application increased for 28,7 %, whereas the increase by poultry manure was 45,4 % compared to synthetic N fertilizer. There are only a few papers on the comparison of manure from different animal species, so this needs to be addressed in the future (Maillard et al., 2014).

N₂O emissions are not only dependent on animal species, but also on the application method of manure. Subsurface manure application significantly increased N₂O emissions by on average 74,8 % relative to synthetic N fertilizers. No significant effects were observed for surface manure application (increase of 17.4 %) (Zhou et al., 2017). However, these findings are not consistent with some other studies (Velthof et al., 2003). Furthermore, subsurface application is widely recommended to reduce NH₃ volatilization, which is a trade-off that has not been well documented so far. N₂O emissions caused by the application of pre-treated manure (e. g. compost) was lower than in case of raw manure application when compared to synthetic N fertilizer (2,8 % and 46,9 % respectively). This difference was caused by contrasting contents of easily degradable C and N compounds. The pre-treated manure may thus offer a potential to mitigate N₂O emissions in agricultural systems.

Significant decreases of N₂O emissions after OM inputs are not often reported. In the revised literature, only two examples were found when different soil textures were compared (Zhou et al., 2017; Shakoor et al., 2021b). Charles et al. (2017) observed greater emissions in fine-textured than in coarse-textured soils. More research studies considering soil texture and OM inputs are needed to fully understand if there is potential for mitigation (Zhou et al., 2017; Shakoor et al., 2021b). Not only soil type impacts N₂O emissions also climate demonstrates to be important since warmer and moister conditions promote microbial processes in soils and significantly increases N₂O emissions in warm temperate climate after OM application (Zhou et al., 2017).

It is difficult to summarize the impacts of OM inputs on N₂O emissions, as outcomes are dependent on the above-mentioned OM properties and pedoclimatic conditions. Especially the contribution of soil characteristics and the impact of OM application method, timing and location on N₂O emissions need to be considered in future research (Guenet et al., 2021; Graham et al., 2017). Experiments comparing different OM inputs with similar C/N ratios should be compared with constant total N rates, as C/N ratios lower than 8 tended to reduce emissions (Graham et al., 2017). Two additional interesting approaches, that also need to be further studied, are the concept of optimum N input rate and optimum yield scaled N₂O emissions (Kim et al., 2017), and integrated nutrient management, based on the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizers to reduce N losses (Graham et al., 2017).

CO₂ emission

Only one relevant meta-analysis dealt with the impact of OM inputs on CO₂ emissions. For farmyard manure and compost, the increase of emissions after OM amendment was not significant, whereas a significant increase was observed after slurry application. However, the number of LTEs included in this study was low (4, 8 and 5), so there is need for new experiments and evaluation of experiments that are running. (Sandén et al., 2018).

Conclusion

In summary, the impact of manure, slurry and compost on SOC is a well-studied topic and reveals a SOC increase, but there is a gap regarding the impact on microbial biomass, N₂O emissions and especially CO₂ emissions and N leaching. There are only few publications that focused on emissions in European field experiments, which provides an opportunity for additional research. The results for N₂O emissions suggest a variety of negative, neutral and even positive effects of OM inputs that should be further studied. However, many authors point out that some important data (properties of OM inputs, soil properties) that are crucial for a holistic understanding of the topic, are missing in the current publications and that this should be improved in the future (Table 17).

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 16: The effect of adding manure, slurry and compost on SOC, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N₂O and CO₂ compared to no fertilization (*) or mineral fertilization (**)

References	Publication level	OM input type	SOC change			MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation	N leaching
Aguilera et al. (2013a) ^{1,*}	Global	compost, manure, agro-industrial wastes				N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
		slurry								
Bolinder et al. (2020) ^{2,*}	Global	manure				N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Chen et al. (2018) ^{1,**}	Global	farmyard manure, livestock manure, manure-based composts				N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
		composts from organic waste								
Gross et al. (2021) ^{1,*}	Global	manure				N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Luo et al. (2018) ^{1,**}	Global	farmyard manure, compost						N/A	N/A	N/A
Maillard et al. (2014) ^{1,*}	Global		cattle	poultry	pig	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
			warm & cool temperate							

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

		manure, compost, slurry	temperate							
Morugán - Coronado et al. (2020) ^{1,**}	Global	manure, compost		N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		
Payen et al. (2021) ^{1,**}	Global	manure, compost, green waste		N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		
Shakoor et al. (2021) ^{b1,*}	Global	manure	N/A	N/A	N/A	coarse texture	medium texture	N/A		
						fine texture				
						acid	neutral	alkaline		
Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ^{2,*}	Global	manure, compost		N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A		
Zhou et al. (2017) ^{1,*}	Global	manure (liquid and solid; composted and raw)		N/A	N/A	cattle	pig	N/A	N/A	
						poultry	farmyard manure		N/A	
						subsurface application	surface application		N/A	
						raw manure	pre-treated manure		N/A	
						warm temperate	cool temperate		N/A	
							temperate		N/A	
						sandy loam	silt clay		sand	N/A
						loam			silt loam	N/A
						clay loam			clay	N/A
						acid	neutral		N/A	
alkaline	N/A									

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

D'Hose et al. (2018) ^{1,**}	EU	farmyard manure, slurry, compost	N/A		N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sandén et al. (2018) ^{1,**}	EU	farmyard manure			N/A			N/A
		compost						N/A
		slurry						N/A
Martyniuk et al. (2019) ^{3,*}	National (EU)	manure			N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SUMMARY						?	?	N/A

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

Control:

*no fertilization; **mineral fertilization

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 17: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on manure, slurry and compost.

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
OM inputs	-Estimations on changes in SOC are difficult to perform since full C input estimations are very scarce.	-Consider all C inputs when investigating changes in SOC stocks after application of external OM.	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹
	-Effects of OM inputs on the dynamics of N, P, etc.	- Experiments should be installed that take into account N and P cycling as well.	Dignac et al. (2017) ² Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	-Does the combination of organic and inorganic amendments increase or decrease the build-up of soil C relative to addition of organic amendments alone. -What is the best method to apply compost to the field in order to minimize N ₂ O emissions	-Install experiments that compare the effect of the combination of organic and inorganic amendments on the build-up of soil C relative to addition of pure organic amendments -Study the duration and method of composting amendments on N ₂ O emissions.	Graham et al. (2017) ²
	-Which factors influence the potential carbon saturation due to OM inputs. -What are the long term effects of fertilizers	-Reassessment of long-term field trials and establishment of new experiments to investigate potential C saturation effects and long-term fertilizer effects.	Gross et al. (2021) ¹
	- What are the long term effects of the additions of organic amendments on N ₂ O emissions.	- Install long-term studies to study the emission of N ₂ O associated with additions of organic amendment since data on this effect are limited.	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	-Only a few studies used pig and poultry manure. -Not many studies compare liquid manure to solid. -It is difficult to estimate the effect of manure amendment to SOC stock changes due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors (C concentration, application rate, dry matter content, animal species).	-Install more experiments that study the effects of pig and poultry manure but also compare effects of liquid manure and solid forms. -Study all properties of manure when applying this in an experiment.	Maillard et al. (2014) ¹ Shakoor et al. (2021) ^{b 1} Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	<p>-Impacts of fresh or pre-processed (composting) organic fertilizer on the stabilization of SOC. -All Benefits and trade-offs of organic fertilizers</p>	<p>-Compare fresh and pre-processed organic fertilizers in new experiment that study the stabilization of SOC -Implement life cycle assessments of organic fertilizers to reveal its benefits and trade-offs.</p>	<p>Tiefenbacher et al. (2021)²</p>
	<p>-What is the SOC saturation level when applying manure to increase SOC? -Evaluation of the trade-offs between GHG emissions and food security regarding manure application.</p>	<p>-Consider a potential saturation of the SOC level following long-term manure application. -Take into account food security as a parameter when studying trade-offs of manure application (e.g. GHG emissions)</p>	<p>Zhou et al. (2017)¹</p>
Pedoclimatic conditions	<p>-Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors</p>	<p>-When studying the effect of soil management strategy, provide information on: 1. initial SOC concentration 2. Bulk density data that allow SOC stock calculations 3. Data on SOC expressed as stock</p> <p>But also, express SOC stocks on an equivalent mass basis.</p>	<p>Aguilera et al. (2013a)¹ Maillard et al. (2014)¹</p>
	<p>-The impact of a soil management strategies on SOC stocks is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered. The impact of soil management strategies on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers is largely unknown. -The impact of the presence of a coarse fraction in soils when calculating SOC stock. This is currently an important source of error in SOC stock estimations. -Accurate calculations/estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors. Calculations via pedotransfer functions bring uncertainty - over- or underestimation of SOC stocks.</p>	<p>-Take into account the effect of soil management strategies on SOC stocks in deeper soil layers -When studying the effect of soil management strategy, provide information on: 1. Coarse fraction 2. Bulk density data that allow SOC stock calculations since this provides more accurate SOC data compared to estimates based on pedotransfer functions</p>	<p>Aguilera et al. (2013a)¹ Payen et al. (2021)¹</p>

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	- Impact of soil properties (texture, drainage, SOC and N content) next to C:N ratio of OM inputs on N ₂ O emissions.	- Study the impact of soil characteristics on N ₂ O emissions.	Graham et al. (2017) ² Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	-The impact of climatic conditions on SOC stock change after manure application	-Additional field studies are required to study the impact of climatic conditions on SOC stock changes.	Gross et al. (2021) ¹ Guenet et al. (2021) ² Maillard et al. (2014) ¹ Payen et al. (2021) ¹
	-Impact of climatic factors (local climate) next to C:N ratio of OM inputs on N ₂ O emissions.	-Additional experiments are required to study the impact of climatic conditions on N ₂ O emissions after OM application	Graham et al. (2017) ² Guenet et al. (2021) ²
		-When reporting studies, these should include a complete overview of the soil physicochemical properties.	Shakoor et al. (2021) ^{b1}
Establishment of experiments	-The effect of soil management strategies on SOC stocks is misrepresented when only surface depths are considered -Information on long term effects of soil management strategies is rare	-When installing new experiments, deeper soil sampling and longer experimental duration need to be considered. This will also reduce data uncertainty.	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹
	-Small quantity of papers showing long-term results on SOC stock changes (lack of LTEs).	-More long term experiments need to be installed	Aguilera et al. (2013a) ¹ Morugán -Coronado et al. (2020) ¹ Zhou et al. (2017) ¹
		-Different types of organic amendments (e.g., manure, compost and green manure from different species) with the same C:N should be paired with constant total N rates. -Future field experiments should evaluate yield-scaled emissions. -Future integrated nutrient management field experiments should include amendments with a range	Graham et al. (2017) ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

		of C:N paired with inorganic N fertilizer at a constant total N rate.	
Other soil management strategies	Information on the impact of soil management strategies in perennial cropping systems is missing.	New experiments should introduced perennial cropping systems when investigating the impact of OM amendments on SOC stocks and the related trade-offs.	Maillard et al. (2014) ¹
Modelling	The understanding of interactions between the C and N cycle need to be improved.	Integrate interactions between C and N cycles in models and improve the understanding of these interactions via experiments.	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
	The impact of climate, soil texture, initial SOC stocks, etc. on SOC stock between and within winegrowing regions, at regional level	Initiate modelling at regional level to investigate the variations of SOC stock responses to the differences in climate, soil texture, initial SOC stocks, etc. between and within winegrowing regions.	Payen et al. (2021) ¹
		Parametrize the quality of organic fertilizers to improve SOC models and reassess the impact of organic fertilizers on SOC pools.	Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) ²
		Improve dynamic biogeochemical models to study interactions between N and C cycle.	Zhou et al. (2017) ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Meta-analysis	The effect of climate, soil texture, manure characteristics etc. on the relationship between cumulative C input and SOC stock change	Determine the effect of climate, soil texture, manure characteristics etc. on the relationship between cumulative C input and SOC stock change using meta-regression with multiple explanatory factors.	Maillard et al. (2014) ¹
Other	Changes in soil C and the embodied GHG costs associated with inorganic N fertilizer and organic amendments are insufficiently quantified and weighed against any increase or decrease in soil N ₂ O.	More studies are required on the method, timing and location of amendment and fertilizer applications on N ₂ O emissions.	Graham et al. (2017) ²
	-Implications of SOC storage potential for crop yields are poorly understood -The consequences of largescale deployment of management options to increase SOC stocks and the constraints related to the nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and potassium (K) cycles are not understood.	-More research on the Implications of SOC storage potential for crop yields are required -More research on the largescale deployment of management options to increase SOC stocks and the constraints related to the nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P) and potassium (K)	Guenet et al. (2021) ²
		A stronger focus on biological soil quality indicators in experiments/projects as well as GHG emissions would enable a better evaluation of trade-offs/ C-N balance and mutual benefits of management practices.	Sandén et al. (2018) ¹
	-Quantitative estimations of the C storage offsets caused by N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions.	Perform quantitative analyses of C sink offsets caused by N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions.	Zhou et al. (2017) ¹

1- Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

3.4.4 Biochar

Biochar effect on SOC change

Biochar is the solid product remaining from the heating of biomass under oxygen depleted conditions and is intended for use in soil or other environmental applications (Lehmann and Joseph, 2015). Biochar has received immense research attention in the last 10 years to investigate its potential efficacy as a solution to climate change (Smith, 2016; Woolf et al., 2010), soil and water pollution remediation (Ahmad et al., 2014), and improving agronomic productivity of soils (Jeffery et al., 2017). Its unique feature in a climate mitigation context is that biochar is more resistant to microbial decomposition compared to the biomass feedstock it was made from and thus persists longer in the soil as a store of carbon (Lehmann et al., 2015). Conversion of biomass to biochar and its deposition in soil can sequester ~50% of the biomass-C. This is much higher than when crop residues are burnt in the field (~ 3%) or via biological degradation of biomass (<10-25% after 5-10 years) (Lehmann et al., 2006). While there is greater confidence considering the soil C sequestration potential of biochar, more research is required to gain more certainty on biochar's net climate change mitigation effect, which must take into account direct and indirect effects on non-CO₂ GHGs, and N leaching losses, but also soil surface albedo (which is generally reduced by biochar application), and indirect emissions which occur in the production of biochar and its associated value chain (Tisserant and Cherubini, 2019).

Biochar effect on GHG emissions

N₂O emissions

Three meta-analysis studies show that on average biochar addition to soils leads to a reduction in N₂O emissions in the range of -9 to -54% (Table 18). Biochar has been shown to reduce N₂O via multiple abiotic and biotic mechanisms including: adsorption and capture of N₂O in biochar pores (Cornelissen et al., 2013), abiotic reduction of N₂O on organo-mineral biochar surfaces (Quin et al., 2015), pH increases leading to more complete microbial denitrification to N₂ (Weldon et al., 2019), and abiotic/biotic synergies where N₂O is transiently held in biochar pores giving more time for denitrifiers to reduce N₂O to N₂ (Harter et al., 2016). While the vast majority of studies show that biochar can mitigate N₂O there is a lack of knowledge available about how long the effect will endure, and which biochar's can be expected to mitigate N₂O under different soils and conditions. Borchard et al. (2019) reviewed 88 studies and found a reduction in NO₃ leaching when biochar was applied in annual cropping systems, while neutral effects were found when biochar was applied in permanent cropping systems such as grassland. Moreover, they found that N₂O mitigation from biochar addition reduced significantly in studies that were conducted >120 days. As observed by Verhoeven et al. (2017), the N₂O mitigation was less pronounced in meta-analyses where only field studies were assessed (-9.2% to -12.4%) compared to meta-analyses that also included short term incubations (Cayuela et al. 2014, -54%). This can be due to field trial artefacts and heterogeneity of biochar distribution at field sites (Kammann et al. 2017) and also due to changes that biochar undergoes as it ages and interacts with soil minerals and organic matter. More studies are needed to show and explain how and why field ageing of biochar reduces its N₂O mitigation effect. There is disagreement in the literature regarding to which extent biochar inhibits or stimulates nitrification rates, and nitrification mediated N₂O emissions (Verhoeven et al., 2017; Wells and Baggs, 2014) with evidence on both sides for increased and decreased N₂O emissions. Sánchez-García et al., 2014 showed that the dominant soil microbial community in a given pedo-climatic soil strongly influences the dominant N₂O pathway (denitrification

vs nitrification) and that a particular biochar can both increase and decrease N₂O emissions in different soils. Authors of meta-analyses recommend greater characterization of biochar's used in studies (Table 19) so that when collated in meta-analysis studies, stronger links may be made between biochar properties and N₂O mitigation impacts (Shakoor et al., 2021b). There is a consistent call from review papers (Kammann et al., 2017, Tammeorg et al. 2016, Zhang et al. 2016) for longer term field studies which also are innovatively designed in order to elucidate on mechanisms of biochar N₂O mitigation under field conditions. Although, this is a limiting factor across most of agricultural research in general and a negative outcome of the prevailing research financing regime.

CH₄ emissions and uptake

We identified three meta-analyses, Jeffery et al. 2016 (42 studies), Cong et al. 2018 (40 studies) and Ji et al. 2018 (61 studies) dealing with the effect of biochar on CH₄ emissions and uptake in soil (Table 18). In Jeffery et al. 2016, biochar was found on average to reduce CH₄ in flooded paddy and acidic soils (Hedges $d=-0.87$), while it reduced the CH₄ sink capacity of neutral and non-flooded soils (Hedges $d = 0.62$). Biochar was also more likely to reduce CH₄ emissions in studies where N application was <120 kg ha⁻¹, which is related to the well-known inhibition effect of N fertilization on methanotrophic bacteria population (Chen et al., 2021). Emission reductions were also observed when biochar was made at temperatures >600 °C, which creates biochars with a greater surface area and minimal labile carbon. However, Cong et al. 2018, who assessed studies conducted up to 2016 and applied a stricter criterion on the influence multiple treatments within studies, found no effect of biochar on CH₄ emissions/uptake in either paddy or upland soils. In contrast, the Ji et al., 2018 meta-analysis found 12% and 72% reduction in CH₄ emissions in paddy and upland soils, but 84% reduction in CH₄ uptake in upland soils. Given the predominance of upland soils in Europe, the potential reduction in CH₄ uptake due to biochar is a cause for concern and requires more research focused on CH₄ uptake dynamics (Ji et al. 2018). Van Zwieten et al. 2015 outlined the need for more research on how CH₄ uptake in soils may be affected via biochar mediated changes in soil gas diffusivity. They also recommended more research on how aged biochar interacts with NH₄ adsorption and how this affects methanotrophic bacterial communities.

Biochar effects on nitrogen leaching

Biochar can both increase and decrease NO₃ leaching losses in soil depending on the type of biochar, its particle size, soil type, and how long biochar has been in the soil (Laird and Rogovska, 2015). Borchard et al., 2019 did a global meta-analysis with 88 lab and field studies and found a -26 to -32% reduction in NO₃ across studies which were conducted >30 days, but ~20% increase in NO₃ leaching for short term studies <30 days (Table 18). This may imply that soil structure disturbance due to biochar addition may be a factor to take into account when assessing biochar influence on leaching. In general, biochar is known to help retain NO₃ in coarse soils due to greater water retention but with the reverse effect in clay soils where it may increase hydraulic conductivity (Laird and Rogovska, 2015). Given the variability in biochar impact on NO₃ leaching, a suggested research need is to develop a functional classification system that can be used to predict NO₃ leaching effects based on soil type, biochar type, and climate interactions (Laird and Rogovska, 2015)

Conclusion

In conclusion, biochar appears to be a promising amendment material for increasing the carbon content of soils with co-benefits for reducing N₂O emissions and NO₃ leaching. There is more

uncertainty about the impact of biochar on CH₄ uptake in upland soils and this is an area for more research. In addition, long term field research which can document the impact of how biochar impacts native soil organic carbon levels and N cycling over time is important to pursue. Due to the variability of biochar types and their functioning in different soils, the continuing research should strive to pinpoint the biochar types and properties which will be best suited for different agronomic and environmental purposes.

Table 18: The effect of biochar on SOC change, N₂O and CH₄ emission and uptake and NO₃ leaching losses compared to control soil without biochar.

References	Publication level	SOC Change	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CH ₄ emission mitigation	N leaching
Borchard et al. 2019 ¹	Global 88 Lab and Field studies		-38%		-26 to -32% in studies >30 days
Cayuela et al. 2014 ¹	Global, 42 Lab and Field studies		-54%		
Cong et al. 2018 ¹	Global –MA				
Jeffery et al. 2016 ¹	Global, Paddy soils			Hedges d = -0.87	
Jeffery et al. 2016 ¹	Global, upland soil (CH ₄ uptake)			Hedges d = 0.62	
Ji et al. 2018 ¹	Global, Paddy soils CH ₄ emission			-12%	
Ji et al. 2018 ¹	Global, Upland soils CH ₄ emission/uptake			-72%	-84% in soil uptake of CH ₄
Verhoeven et al. 2017 ¹	Global Field only		--9.2 to -12.4%		
SUMMARY					

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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Table 19: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses and reviews on biochar

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Biochar	Fate of Biochar-DOC	Determine the extent of loss and mineralization of Biochar derived DOC	Tisserant and Cherubini 2018 ¹
	Effects of feedstock and pyrolysis conditions on N ₂ O	Need for more mechanistic studies to unravel the effects of feedstock, pyrolysis process conditions, and the optimal physio-chemical properties of biochar to mitigate N ₂ O	Cayuela et al. 2014 ¹
	Duration effect of N ₂ O mitigation. Many studies observe effects but more needed to unravel mechanisms.	Need for lifecycle GHG assessments when using biochar as an on-farm management tool for nutrient-rich biomass waste streams	Kammann et al 2017 ²
	Knowledge of biochar-induced effects on soil N ₂ O emissions especially on grassland and perennial crops is incomplete.	The eco-physiological mechanisms controlling N uptake by plants in soil-biochar-plant systems require further analyses to ensure sustainable N-management.	Borchard et al. 2019 ¹
	Interactive effects in soil	Studies on Biochar and CH ₄ should consider interactions of soil properties when assessing the biochar impacts on CH ₄	Cong et al. 2018 ¹
	More knowledge is needed to discern under which environmental conditions biochar increases and decreases CH ₄ . The underlying mechanism why biochar made from lignocellulosic waste leads to a significantly decreased CH ₄ sink strength/increased source strength. Integral information on biochar properties may contribute to new insights.	When installing new experiments it is important to provide biochar properties such as pH and surface area. High surface area chars reduced CH ₄ more.	Jeffery et al. 2016 ¹
	CH ₄ uptake in upland soils	More field trials needed to elucidate mechanisms for	Ji et al. 2016 ¹

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

		biochar reduction of CH ₄ uptake in upland soils	
		More studies on CH ₄ fluxes and cycling needed	Tammeorg et al 2016 ²
Pedoclimatic conditions	Effect of biochar on the rhizosphere microbiome	More research on the modifications of the rhizosphere microbiome induced by biochar is needed.	Tammeorg et al 2016 ²
	Priming of native SOM	More research needed on SOM priming effect from biochar	Tammeorg et al 2016 ²
	Effect of biochar application on N balance	Nitrogen balance (e.g., plant N uptake, remaining soil N, and nitrate leaching losses) need to be studied.	Tammeorg et al 2016 ²
Establishment of experiments	How to adjusted biomarker methods for applications with biochar. Methods for biomarker extraction may be compromised by adsorption of biomarkers to biochar surfaces.	-Need for development biochar adjusted biomarker methods	Tammeorg et al 2016 ²
	Confirmation of underlying mechanism via field research confirmation	Need for long term field research but with innovative techniques which can give mechanistic explanations	Zhang et al. 2016 ² , Amonette et al. 2020 ² , Tammeorg et al. 2016 ² , Kammann et al. 2017 ²
Other soil management strategies	N/A	N/A	N/A
Modelling	N/A	N/A	N/A
Meta-Analysis	N/A	N/A	N/A
Other	There is insufficient information yet for how to best upscale biochar production in soil/climate agro-economic systems that could benefit from its use	More studies with biochar made at commercial scale	Zhang et al. 2016 ²
	How to make the biochar production technology more efficient	long-term studies of biochar production and application to answer questions about the technology's cost and potential impact, and to guide future development.	Amonette et al. 2020 ²

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	The amount of gas emissions related to producing biochar	More measurements on gas emissions from commercial pyrolysis plants in order to assess LCA effects	Tisserant and Cherubini 2018 ¹
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3.4.5 Liming

Effects of liming on SOC change

The impact of different liming amendments on soil organic carbon (SOC) was observed in various studies (Table 20). Some studies have found a neutral effect on SOC with the addition of dolomite (Abalos et al., 2020), lime (Paradelo et al., 2015) and sugar beet lime with red gypsum (Vazquez et al., 2020). There were no differences in SOC content in limed croplands. The increased C inputs may have compensated for the increased respiration, resulting in no net differences in terms of SOC. Furthermore, this research was done on a coarse sandy soil where lack of physical protection of soil organic matter (SOM) can affect SOC content (Abalos et al., 2020). Literature reviewed by Paradelo et al. (2015) show variable effects of liming on SOC, which are difficult to explain, given that lime is generally applied to croplands in combination with other fertilizers. As a consequence, more research is needed to unravel the interactions effect of liming with other agricultural management practices. Lime amendments to organic and acid soils resulted in neutral effect on SOC. This was likely due to an increase in pH which on its turn stimulates microbial activity favoring SOM mineralization, especially when absence of mineral complexes leads to negligible physical protection of SOM (Paradelo et al., 2015).

In some studies, lime application resulted in positive effects on SOC and increases of 5,8 % were observed (Eze et al., 2018). In addition, increasing dolomite application rates increased the dissolved organic carbon (DOC) contents (Shaaban et al., 2019). However, a short-term incubation study of Lochon et al. (2018) showed negative effects of liming on SOC. The addition of lime resulted in increased O₂ consumption (10,3 %) and thus SOC mineralization. This increase was due to a concurrent increase in soil pH and consequently modifying microbial activity, increasing resource availability and microbial C-use efficiency and/or altering microbial community structure (Lochon et al., 2018).

In the reviewed literature some knowledge gaps are mentioned (Table 21). Indeed, changes in SOC stocks in the organic upper soil layers after liming have been consistently observed and published. In turn, the evidence is scarce for mineral (deeper) soil layers, where trends are more difficult to identify. Furthermore, result of different studies cannot be easily compared, due to e.g., the differences in site properties and experimental design, liming treatments and rates, soil type, land use, tillage, vegetation, sampling procedures and time span of the experiment. In addition, critical data such as bulk density, plant productivity or C inputs from vegetation are often missing in these studies. A focus on the mechanisms of SOC accumulation and physical protection of SOM and formation of organo-mineral complexes in mineral soils is needed when developing new experimental studies or to modify ongoing experimental studies to fully understand the effects of this widespread agricultural practice. Also projected changes in climatic conditions (warming, drought, wetter conditions) and the contribution of different microbial groups to better understand the interactions between soil responses to liming should be considered.

Effects of liming on GHG emissions

Review of the literature found that, on balance, liming increased soil C content mostly because it increased crop yields and therefore residue returns. Park Grass experiment at Rothamsted spanning 129 years show that net C sequestration measured in the 0–23 cm layer at different time intervals since 1876 was 2–20 times greater in limed than in un-limed soils: the greater biological activity in limed soils, despite increasing soil respiration rates, led to plant C inputs being processed and

incorporated into resistant soil organo-mineral pools more effectively (Goulding, 2016). It can be therefore concluded that liming might be an effective mitigation strategy against climate change (Fornara et al., 2011). However, this has to be balanced against the emissions of CO₂ when lime neutralizes acidity in soils (Paradelo et al., 2015; Goulding, 2016).

Regarding N₂O emissions, the addition of various liming amendments has a positive effect on the reduction of N₂O emissions (Abalos et al., 2020; Khaliq et al., 2019; Shaaban et al., 2019; Vazquez et al., 2020; Zaman et al., 2010) (Table 20). Liming treatment with sugar beet lime and red gypsum reduced the cumulative N₂O emission by more than 70 and 65% respect to the unamended soil after the soil was rewetted to 50% and 100% of field capacity, respectively (Vazquez et al., 2020). In the research of Abalos et al. (2020) the addition of dolomite significantly reduced N₂O emissions by 40 to 82 % and by 44 to 52 % in research of Khaliq et al. (2019). In the latter study the use of lime (CaCO₃) and dolomite (CaMg(CO₃)₂) was compared. Lime amendment reduced N₂O emissions, by 37 to 44 %, but the changes in reducing N₂O emissions were greater in dolomite treatment (Khaliq et al., 2019). A study by Zaman et al. (2010) compared the addition of lime and zeolite, where zeolite application reduced the N₂O emissions, while lime had no effect on N₂O emissions.

Potential mitigation of agronomic practices (liming and tillage) on N₂O pulses is still poorly understood and studies of their effects are scarce. It was recommended to investigate the effects of long-term manipulation of soil properties on N₂O emission under field conditions, to evaluate the impact of different liming materials on soil N₂O emissions to study its life cycle and its potential as a mitigation practice for N₂O emissions.

Besides N₂O emissions, CO₂ emissions derived from soil after lime application should also be considered as GHG mitigation strategy. According to the reviewed literature, many studies indicate that liming increases CO₂ emissions (Abalos et al., 2020; Dietzen et al., 2018; Lochon et al., 2018). Dolomite liming increased CO₂ respiration fluxes from soil in a study of Abalos et al. (2020), but there were no differences between liming rates. Negative effects on CO₂ emissions could also be identified after addition of lime (CaCO₃). Indeed, lime increased CO₂ emissions by 29,5 % (Lochon et al., 2018) and by 221 % compared to a control (Dietzen et al., 2018). In this study olivine (magnesium iron silicate (Mg²⁺, Fe²⁺)₂SiO₄) amendment was also investigated. Olivine proved to be a suitable replacement for lime, since the CO₂ emissions were reduced (Dietzen et al., 2018). However, Egan et al. (2017) found a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions in treatments that received applications of agricultural lime (CaCO₃) on a long-time field experiment (since year 1991), thus long-term experiments are required (Egan et al., 2017).

Current CO₂ budget calculations consider lime-induced emissions of CO₂ as a fixed factor and may therefore contribute to inaccuracies in estimates of the global warming potential of agricultural practices. The generality of findings should be tested for a broader range of soil types and climatic conditions. Future studies should also examine the contribution of different microbial groups to better understand the interactions between soil responses to liming (Lochon et al., 2018).

Effects of liming on nitrogen leaching loss

Only one study was reviewed for N leaching. Bergholm et al. (2015) analyzed the fate of inorganic soil N over four years (1992–1995) in a new clear-cut. N leaching at 50 cm depth was dominated by NO₃-N and culminated during the second year in lime-amended treatment and during third year in control treatment. Cumulative N leaching for the four-year period was lower for a treatment with lime (31 kg

N/ha) than for the control (53 kg N/ha) and was inversely correlated with plant N uptake. Nitrogen immobilization in stumps and root necromass (including spruce and grass roots) was calculated to be 35–45 kg N/ha during this period. The four-year N balance showed 5–17 % higher inputs (net mineralization and deposition) than outputs (plant uptake, leaching, immobilization in dead stumps/roots and accumulation of inorganic N). A novel finding was that lime application, although stimulating nitrification, also stimulated plant N uptake which reduced nitrate leaching in comparison with the control (Bergholm et al., 2015). There is a need for more studies investigating liming effects on N leaching. Also, it was emphasized that quantitative data on gaseous N losses (NO, N₂O and N₂) are scarce (Bergholm et al., 2015).

Conclusion

To conclude, liming most often stimulates SOC stocks, what seems to be caused by higher C inputs to limed soils due to increased crop biomass productivity. Reductions in SOC have also been reported, which may be explained by increased mineralization, whereas the role of improved soil structure remains unclear. Liming mitigated N₂O emissions through an increased N₂O reduction to N₂, but also by enhancing plant growth and thus plant N uptake. As a strategy, stimulating the growth and activity of plants and soil microorganisms, liming can increase CO₂ flux through soil respiration. Such negative impact might be outweighed by increasing SOC stock in soils characterized by a high C sequestration potential. This is not the case for sandy soils (Abalos et al., 2020). By consuming anthropogenic CO₂ and reducing agricultural CO₂ emissions, enhanced silicate weathering has proved to have the potential to serve as an important part of the solution to the problem of elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (Dietzen et al., 2018). By applying finely ground silicate minerals to soils silicate weathering enhances the rate of carbon sequestration. For example, Dietzen et al. (2018) investigated olivine amendment to soil. Weathering of olivine by carbonic acid consumes twice as much CO₂ as the dissolution of lime, making olivine a more effective soil amendment with respect to carbon sequestration. However, the weathering effect of strong acids also needs consideration when assessing the carbon sequestration potential of silicate minerals, particularly when soil pH is below 5 (Dietzen et al., 2018).

Based on the results of numerous reviewed studies, research on liming affecting potential trade-offs and synergies all together (carbon sequestration, microbial biomass C and N, N₂O and CO₂ emissions and N leaching) is lacking. Especially long-term field experiments are needed where effects of different liming amendments are studied. In addition, the effects of liming on plant inputs to the soil, which affect the overall carbon balance, needs further investigations. Finally, these effects need to be studied along with different soil management practices.

Table 20: The impact of liming (lime, dolomite, olivine, zeolite, sugar beet lime with red gypsum) on SOC sequestration, microbial biomass- Carbon (MBC) and -Nitrogen (MBN), emissions of N₂O and CO₂, and N leaching losses compared to no amendment.

References	Publication level	SOC change	MBC	MBN	N ₂ O emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation	N leaching
Dietzen et al. (2018) ³	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	olivine lime	N/A
Eze et al. (2018) ¹	Global	lime	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Khaliq et al. (2019) ³	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	Dolomite	lime	N/A	N/A
Paradelo et al. (2015) ²	Global	lime	N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A	N/A
Shaaban et al. (2019) ³	Global	dolomite	dolomite	N/A	dolomite		N/A	N/A
Zaman et al. (2010) ³	Global	N/A	N/A	N/A	lime	zeolite	N/A	N/A
Abalos et al. (2020) ³	National (in EU)	dolomite	N/A	N/A	dolomite		dolomite	N/A
Bergholm et al. (2015) ³	National (in EU)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		N/A	lime
Egan et al. (2018) ³	National (in EU)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A		lime	N/A
Lochon et al. (2018) ³	National (in EU)	lime	lime	N/A	N/A		lime	N/A
Vazquez et al. (2020) ³	Regional (SW Spain)	sugar beet lime + red gypsum	N/A	N/A	sugar beet lime+red gypsum		N/A	N/A
SUMMARY				N/A			?	lime

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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Table 21: Knowledge gaps and research recommendations indicated in the meta-analyses, reviews, and original articles on liming

Group	Knowledge gaps	Research recommendations	Authors
Liming	- effects of liming on SOC stocks remain poorly known - evidence on the impact of liming on SOC stocks is scarce for mineral soils and horizons, where trends are more difficult to identify	Long-term field experiments specialized on liming are needed across EU.	Paradelo et al. (2015) ² Goulding (2016) ²
	- the impact of several liming materials on soil N ₂ O emissions	- evaluate different liming material's impact on soil N ₂ O emissions	Shaaban et al. (2019) ³

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-The GHG mitigation potential of CO ₂ emissions derived from the CaCO ₃ dissolution in soil after application upon rewetting	- besides N ₂ O emissions, CO ₂ emissions derived from the CaCO ₃ dissolution in soil after application upon rewetting should also be considered as GHG mitigation strategy	Vazquez et al. (2020) ³
	-potential of zeolite as a mitigating tool for N ₂ O emissions	- long-term field studies are required to assess zeolite life cycle and its potentials as a mitigating tool for N ₂ O emissions	Zaman et al. (2010) ³
Pedoclimatic conditions	- impact of liming on no net differences of SOC by the lack of SOM physical protection and low formation of organo-mineral complexes in coarse sandy soils	-Study the impact of liming on SOC stocks evolution and SOM physical protection in coarse sandy soils	Abalos et al. (2020) ³
	- not clear to what extent effects of treatments (grazing, liming, insecticides, and inorganic nutrients, amendments) on soil aggregates were mediated by changes in plant species composition		Egan et al. (2018) ³
	-Underlying mechanisms of SOC accumulation -Accurate calculations/ estimations of SOC stock changes are difficult to due to a lack of essential information provided by many authors.	- focus on mechanisms of SOC accumulation in new experimental studies or modify ongoing studies - When studying the effect of soil management strategy, provide critical information on: 1.bulk density 2.plant productivity 3.C inputs from vegetation are often missing	Paradelo et al. (2015) ²
	- climate change effects on temperate grasslands remain poorly understood - how will projected changes in climatic conditions (warming, drought, wetter conditions) influence SOC storage and fluxes - net effect of management activities on the balance of greenhouse gasses	- start more site-specific experiments that study interactive effects of climate change and grassland management activities such as fertilizer application and liming under different grazing regimes on SOC stocks and GHG emissions	Eze et al. (2018) ¹
	The general impact of liming on CO ₂ emissions, in different soils and climatic conditions	- investigate the impact of liming on CO ₂ emissions a broader range of soil types and climatic conditions	Lochon et al. (2018) ³
Establishment of experiments	- Impact on NO, N ₂ O and N ₂ emissions are poorly studied - extrapolation of mineralization/ nitrification rate to field conditions according to temperature and moisture corrections	- Study the impact on gaseous N losses (NO, N ₂ O and N ₂) to obtain quantitative data	Bergholm et al. (2015) ³

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

	-Long term effects of liming -Insight in initial CO ₂ fluxes	-Use longer incubation periods in experiments -Install long term field studies to assess potential changes in plant inputs affecting the overall carbon balance	Dietzen et al. (2018) ³
		- Start the initial CO ₂ flux measurement immediately at the beginning of treatments application in order to cover all emission peaks	Egan et al. (2018) ³
Other soil management strategies	- interaction between liming with inorganic and organic nutrient fertilization	-Start new experiments to investigate the interaction between liming with inorganic and organic nutrient fertilization	Egan et al. (2018) ³
	-long term effects of manipulation of soil properties on N ₂ O emissions under field conditions are poorly understood	- focus on effects of long-term manipulation of soil properties on N ₂ O emissions under field conditions	Khaliq et al. (2019) ³
	- Impact of N inputs and historical management intensity on lime-induced benefits and lime-induced CO ₂ emissions	- Consider N inputs and historical management intensity when assessing lime-induced benefits against lime-induced CO ₂ emissions	Lochon et al. (2018) ³
	- potential mitigation of agronomic practices on N ₂ O pulses is still poorly understood - effects of no-till practice on N ₂ O emission from (limed) soils after rewetting are poorly studied		Vazquez et al. (2020) ³
Meta-analysis	- published SOC data are still scarce - the acquisition of new insights via meta-analysis is often impeded because comparisons between studies cannot be easily accomplished, due to the differences in site properties and experimental design	- Organize (field) experiments in cooperation with other researcher to obtain sets of complementary experiments and to achieve stronger datasets that allow comparisons between studies	Paradelo et al. (2015) ²
Modelling	-Quantification of lime induced CO ₂ emissions: current CO ₂ budget calculations consider lime-induced emissions of CO ₂ as a fixed factor		Lochon et al. (2018) ³
Other (Microorganisms)	-insight in fungal immobilization of nitrogen		Bergholm et al. (2015) ³
	-To obtain a better understanding of the soil responses to liming more insight in the role of different microbial groups is required	- examine the contribution of different microbial groups to better understand the interactions between soil responses to liming	Lochon et al. (2018) ³

1. Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

4. Summary and Conclusion

With this report, the SOMMIT-project synthesizes the state-of-the-art knowledge, knowledge gaps, and research recommendations on trade-offs and synergies between SOC sequestration on the one hand and N₂O- and CH₄- emissions and N leaching on the other hand. We summarized the effects of the most important soil management strategies on trade-offs and synergies in terms of SOC stock change, MBC, MBN, soil GHG emissions, and nitrogen leaching losses. This report was compiled via a dedicated literature study carried out by eight research institutes across Europe. After the selection of the search criteria (e.g., type of literature, land use, time-period, and research origin) 110 unique literature items were analyzed.

4.1 Current knowledge (gaps) on trade-offs and synergies on specific soil management strategy categories

The overall effects of the soil management strategies which were included in the literature analysis are summarized in Table 22. Generally, this report highlights that the increase of both SOC stock change and the microbial biomass C and N, as well as the reduction in NO₃⁻ leaching are positively affected by conservation tillage, crop rotation, permanent cropping, more efficient water management as well as using fertilization and OM inputs (e.g., cover crops, organic amendments, biochar, and liming). The effects on the N₂O and CH₄ emission mitigation are dependent on the specific soil management strategy (e.g., water management, fertilization and OM inputs) and require more research to allow to define (uniform) conclusions.

Tillage management: Conservation tillage strategies such as no-tillage and minimum tillage, generally favor an increase of the SOC content in the topsoil by redistributing SOC towards the soil surface. The effect of tillage management on N₂O emissions should be further investigated since literature does not provide unambiguous results. Only one study with a focus on tillage management included in our literature analysis simultaneously estimated SOC stock changes, GHG emissions, and NO₃⁻ leaching under different tillage systems (Autret et al., 2019). The authors observed a positive effect on SOC change and CO₂ emission mitigation. Based on the available literature, it is not possible yet to define (uniform) conclusions about the effect of tillage management on N₂O and CH₄ emission mitigation, N leaching, MBC and MBN.

Cropping Systems: Cropping systems and SOC dynamics are strictly linked. Some combined crop sequences and soil management practices such as crop rotation and the use of legumes with conservation tillage or organic agricultural systems can enhance SOC storage. Generally, the adoption of diversified crop rotations contributes to enhanced MBC and MBN levels in agricultural soils compared to the monocropping systems. Regarding N₂O emissions, a clear picture on the trade-offs between N₂O emissions and SOC did not emerge. However, it is highlighted that permanent cropping systems in conservation and organic agriculture can reduce N₂O emissions compared to annual cropping systems. Similarly, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions and NO₃ leaching were both reduced in organic agricultural systems. CO₂ and CH₄ emissions were also reduced when using an agroforestry system and crop rotations, respectively. NO₃ leaching on its turn was also reduced when cover crops and especially legumes were introduced into the crop rotation. More studies on MBC, MBN, CH₄ emission mitigation and N leaching are required to allow to define (uniform) conclusions about different cropping system practices since at this moment only information on a limited number of practices is available.

Water Management: Irrigation favors the increase of crop yield and biomass production, which may lead to an increased SOC stock via larger carbon inputs. Such SOC stock increase has been observed under sprinkler and drip irrigation, but not in flood and furrow irrigated soils. The combination of

irrigation with conservation tillage stimulates SOC contents. Nevertheless, irrigation induces trade-offs, especially with GHG emissions. Several studies observed that the increased level of soil moisture and the availability of reactive nitrogen compounds due to irrigation management stimulates N₂O emissions. Also, irrigation management can favor CO₂ emissions due to the increase of soil microbial activity. In addition, water management practices in general stimulate N leaching. More information on the impact of water management on CH₄ emission mitigation, MBC and MBN is required to allow to define (uniform) conclusions.

Fertilization and Organic matter input: In this group, the following fertilization and organic amendments have been considered: crop residues, cover crop, livestock manure, slurry, compost, biochar, and liming.

Crop Residues: The effect of crop residues on SOC content has been well studied globally and at European level. Straw C/N ratio is the main factor determining the accumulation of SOC as well as the variability of the N₂O emission and NO₃⁻ leaching response after residue addition. The use of crop residues positively influences SOC stock changes, MBC- and MBN levels and reduce N leaching. Crop residues seems to affect N₂O emission mitigation in a negative way. However, more research on this mitigation and the emission of CO₂ and CH₄ is required to obtain better insight in the effect on GHG emissions.

Cover crop (Green manure): The studies evaluated in this report highlight that the trade-offs and synergies between SOC change and GHG emissions are mostly influenced by the CC type. For instance, the use of legume CC shows trade-offs between SOC change and N₂O emissions. A clear synergy was observed between SOC increase and N leaching reduction for non-legumes, both at global and EU level. The use of cover crops generally positively affected MBC and MBN levels in agricultural soils. More information on the impact of CC on CH₄ emission mitigation across Europe is required.

Livestock manure, slurry, and compost: The impact of these OM inputs on SOC stock change and microbial biomass has been well-investigated and revealed a stimulation of both the SOC content and microbial biomass compared to the other organic (cover crops, crop residues) or inorganic fertilizers. These stimulations tend to be stronger with application of more stabilized OM forms (e.g., compost) compared to liquid OM (e.g., slurries) which are characterized by highly decomposable C. The stability of OM in organic amendments also impacts the dynamics of mineral N release to crops and potentially leached N into the groundwater. To date, there are only few publications that specifically focused on the effects of livestock manure, slurry, and compost on (the combination of) GHG emissions and NO₃⁻ leaching monitoring at European level. More information and additional research are required to allow to define (uniform) conclusions.

Biochar: During last decade, biochar has been receiving increasing research attention because of its potential efficacy to mitigate climate change by improving agronomic productivity of soils. Indeed, biochar seems to be a promising organic amendment able to increase the C content of soils compared to other OM inputs because its recalcitrance to microbial decomposition. Most studies demonstrated that biochar can positively stimulate SOC stock change but also mitigates N₂O emissions. However, more information on the impact of biochar on CH₄ emission mitigation in European upland soils is required to allow to define (uniform) conclusions. Since biochar generally favors the retention of NO₃ in coarse soils due to greater water retention, it thus reduces NO₃⁻ leaching.

Liming: In the reviewed literature a positive effect of liming on MBC was observed due to the increased crop biomass productivity that provided higher C inputs into the soils compared non-limed soils. Despite this, liming induced a neutral effect on SOC stock changes. However, more research is needed to confirm these observations. Application of liming as amendment mitigates N₂O emissions

and reduces NO_3^- leaching. According to the reviewed literature, some studies indicate that liming stimulates CO_2 emissions, others suggest the opposite. However, there is a strong need for more studies investigating the liming effects on CO_2 mitigation. In addition, also the effects of liming on MBN must be better investigated to define conclusions at European level.

SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

Table 22: The effect of soil management strategies on SOC change, GHG emissions, microbial biomass nitrogen and carbon, and N leaching.

Soil management strategy	SOC change		N ₂ O emission mitigation		MBC	MBN	CH ₄ emission mitigation	CO ₂ emission mitigation		N leaching	
Tillage management			?		N/A	N/A	?			?	
Cropping systems	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS		CONS; CC; CC incorporated into the soil; CG; CF	CONS; ORG; PER	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS	ROT; LEG; ORG; CONS	ORG; AGF; CG; CF	ORG; PER, ROT		CC; LEG; ORG	
Water Management					N/A	N/A	?				
Fertilization and OM input – Crop residues							N/A	?			
Fertilization and OM input – Cover crops							N/A				
Fertilization and OM input – Livestock manure, slurry and compost			?				N/A	?		N/A	
Fertilization and OM input – Biochar					N/A	N/A		N/A			
Fertilization and OM input – Liming						N/A	N/A	?			

Table legend (also see Chapter 2):

N/A: Not Assessed; no-tillage (zero-till); non-inversion tillage (minimum/ reduced tillage); legume non-legume

Type of study:

1-Meta-analysis; 2- Review; 3-Original paper

Impact: Positive (green color), negative (red color), no difference (grey color)

positive	negative	neutral
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4.2 Knowledge gaps and research recommendations

The knowledge gaps have been revealed via a screening of published meta-analyses, reviews, original papers, and reports - with attention to long-term field experiments - at global and European levels (regional, national, and European Union), covering contrasting agro-environmental conditions. The report identified the most important agricultural soil management strategies, which were grouped into the following categories: tillage management, cropping systems, water management, and fertilization and organic matter inputs (i.e., crop residues, cover crops, manure, slurry and compost, biochar, and liming).

Although the four categories are strongly connected, this report considers knowledge gaps and research recommendations separately for each category, grouped into following main topics: pedoclimatic conditions, establishment of the experiments, other soil management strategies, meta-analysis, and modelling. This unique combination of knowledge gaps and research recommendations provides a solid basis to help to (re-)design dedicated experiments to improve our understandings of these impacts. The research recommendations provided in this report help the main stakeholders to identify important combinations of agricultural soil management strategies that need to be investigated to improve soil carbon sequestration and limit GHG emissions and NO₃ leaching losses.

Knowledge gaps and research recommendations on pedoclimatic conditions

The review of the literature on the four soil management categories identified the lack of information on the impact of pedoclimatic conditions on the trade-offs and synergies (Guenet et al., 2021; Hu et al., 2018; Lochon et al., 2018). Thus, soil management strategies should be better investigated in different agro-environmental zones (Gross et al., 2021; Guenet et al., 2021; Maillard et al., 2014; Payen et al., 2021), because pedoclimatic conditions strongly influence the soil C and N dynamics (Eze et al., 2018).

More specifically, knowledge on the impact of soil management strategies on SOC stock is needed. Despite the availability of published data on soil C contents, these data do often not allow to accurately calculate the effects on SOC stocks in e.g., meta-analyses. Indeed, several authors (Aguilera et al., 2013a, b, Emde et al., 2021, Millard and Angers, 2014) pointed out the lack of measured data on soil bulk density, necessary to calculate SOC stocks. The use of pedotransfer functions to estimate soil bulk density can bring uncertainty in the evaluation of SOC stocks (Aguilera et al. 2013a; Jian et al. 2020; Payen et al. 2021), and thus, must be avoided in a meta-analysis. Furthermore, the report shows that SOC stock changes, GHG emissions, and NO₃⁻ leaching are influenced by pedoclimatic conditions and that there is a lack of understanding on the impact of these pedoclimatic conditions. While agro-environmental zones of Northern, Central, Southern, and Western Europe are relatively well investigated, there is a lack of studies comprising eastern regions of Europe. Also, it highlights that the availability of datasets concerning the investigated practices thus varies among agro-environmental zones. These lacks make it difficult to draw a general conclusion and indicate that further research to fill these knowledge gaps and produce datasets is required.

Furthermore, there is a knowledge gap on the effects of soil management practices on the subsoil, due to the limited studies that investigate the subsoil below the plough level, as reported by Aguilera et al. (2013a), Emde et al. (2021), and Poeplau and Don (2015). Hence, the effects of tillage systems, water management, and cover crop (types and termination strategies) on SOC stock are misrepresented when only shallow layers are considered. Moreover, the lack of a full estimation of organic C inputs and non-accounting of the coarse fraction are important sources of errors in SOC stock estimation,

which is reported as a crucial knowledge gap by Aguilera et al. (2013a), Muhammad et al. (2019), Payen et al. (2021).

Most of the studies that have been reviewed in this report agree that the interaction effects of agricultural soil management strategies (e.g., irrigation, fertilization and organic matter input) and soil properties should be better investigated (Chen et al., 2013; Guenet et al., 2021; Shakoor et al., 2021b; Wang et al., 2018). Indeed, these can considerably influence SOC stocks and GHG emissions, especially N₂O and CO₂ emissions. Particularly, understanding how SOC dynamics and GHG emissions are affected by soil properties (e.g., pH, texture, or other physico-chemical properties) and irrigation (Emde et al., 2021) or by fertilization and organic matter inputs (e.g., crop residues and cover crops) as observed by Chen et al. (2013) and Quemada et al. (2013) is important to enhance the efficacy of global efforts aimed at offsetting GHG emissions and N leaching via SOC sequestration.

In the reviewed literature, climate change is usually not considered, although it is known that this will have an important impact on SOC stock change, GHG emissions, and NO₃ leaching losses. Therefore, the global meta-analysis of Eze et al. (2018) highlighted that more site-specific field experiments focusing on the interactive effects of climate change and agricultural soil management practices, such as fertilizer application and liming under different grazing regimes should be better investigated. Also, to better assess the effects on potential trade-offs, researchers suggested to investigate the impacts of climatic factors on N₂O and NO₃⁻ leaching (e.g., Wang et al., 2018), especially in dry cool temperate (Xia et al., 2018) and dry warm climatic zones (e.g., Abdalla et al., 2019; Basche et al., 2014, Quemada et al., 2013)

Knowledge gaps and research recommendations on the establishment of experiments

Many aspects related to the establishment of experiments such as the selection of more appropriate experimental duration, site selection, type of measurements, experimental scale (field/pot/laboratory incubation), but also data availability can strongly contribute to the improvement of our insights on trade-offs and synergies (e.g., Haddaway et al., 2017). LTEs are a valuable resource to reveal how different crop sequence and soil management practices contribute to soil C and N dynamics.

Generally, the duration of experiments and monitoring is short- (usually less than 12 months) or medium-term as detected by analyzing the literature focused on tillage management (Dignac et al., 2017), cropping systems (Autret et al., 2019), irrigation management (Aguilera et al., 2013b; Cayuela et al., 2017), and fertilization and organic matter input (Lehtinen et al., 2014). This can result to irregular conclusions for the effect of time and management on SOC changes (Bolinder et al., 2020) and GHG emissions which on its turn can contribute to the underestimation of N₂O emission factor (EF). For instance, Emde et al. (2021) reported that information regarding monitoring of irrigation management over long-term (>15 years) is notably limited. Similarly, Dietzen et al. (2018) investigated the effect of fertilization and organic matter input on CO₂ emissions and highlighted that long-term field studies are needed to better assess potential changes in plant inputs affecting the overall carbon balance. Therefore, longer monitoring of experimental sites (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2017; Zornoza et al., 2018) is needed to better assess the effects of tillage systems (Payen et al., 2021), crop diversification (Autret et al., 2019), and irrigation methods (Emde et al., 2021) on SOC stock change and GHG emissions, especially CO₂ and N₂O (Hénault et al., 2012; Lehtinen et al., 2014).

Regarding the type of measurements and data availability, it is well-known that conservation tillage generally increases the SOC content in the topsoil (0-30 cm soil depth), but the effect of reduced tillage on the soil profile is controversial because studies reporting data on SOC stock below plough layer are limited and further research is required. Moreover, an ongoing debate remains on how different tillage systems affect GHG emission, particularly N₂O.

As reported by Sandén et al. (2018), field experiments should focus more on biological soil quality indicators and GHG emissions to better evaluate the trade-offs and mutual benefits of management practices. Moreover, as observed by Siedt et al. (2021) for fertilization and organic matter input (crop residues management), experiments at constant laboratory conditions are not suitable, because many important effects can be masked. Indeed, the lack of sufficiently robust field data does impede accurate estimations and conclusions on the possible trade-offs among SOC sequestration, GHG emissions, and NO_3^- leaching as reported by Hansen et al. (2019), Lugato et al. (2018), and Poeplau and Don (2015). To better understand the impact of soil management strategies on trade-offs between SOC sequestration and GHG emissions and NO_3^- leaching more studies with a longer temporal scale that consider the combined effects of different soil management practices should be established.

Knowledge gaps and research recommendations on other soil management strategies

Most of the reviewed studies describe that a major cause of current knowledge gaps is the lack of research that assesses the combined and synergetic effects of soil management strategy categories (e.g., tillage management, cropping systems, and fertilization and organic matter input) on SOC storage, GHG emissions and nitrogen leaching. Indeed, most of the studies nowadays still investigate the effect of a single management practice as a stand-alone practice, which is far from assessing the effects of combined management practices as they occur in real farming systems. Also, there is a need to improve the understanding of how the management measures adopted in different management systems such as organic agriculture contribute to C inputs and retention in soils. However, also research on e.g., the amount of crop residue that can be removed must be performed since this amount will depend on soil types, climate conditions, and management systems (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2010). In this context, McDaniel et al. (2014) suggested that data from long-term field experiments with different crop management and cropping systems may provide valuable insights on C inputs and on SOC changes. Similarly, further investigations on combined effects of tillage and fertilizer and organic matter input on SOC is required to determine under what conditions manure application can increase soil C storage and crop productivity without increasing N_2O emissions (Guenet et al., 2021; Haddaway et al., 2017; Kuang et al., 2021). Xia et al. (2018) stressed the importance of investigating the fraction of N lost as N_2O or NO_3^- leaching in different soils, which receive mineral nitrogen or straw with different C/N ratios, to better understand the interaction between C and N cycles.

Finally, Kim et al. (2016) and Hu et al. (2018) highlighted the importance of more in-depth investigations of the contribution of C inputs from roots, root-exudates, and rhizodeposition to SOC stock change and C sequestration rate, during the crop growth period. Recently, Jansson et al. (2021) have suggested to improve the knowledge about the contribution of plant photosynthate to belowground biomass. This is because it directly influences the C source-sink interactions in an integrated plant-microbe-soil system. In this perspective, they argued that belowground carbon allocation should be increased by larger and deeper root biomass as well as by soil microbiome and plant interactions.

Knowledge gaps and research recommendations on meta-analysis

An important limitation of meta-analysis that has been identified in this report is that authors do often do not report the soil depth considered in the investigated studies. Moreover, they generally do not account for unequal precision in the magnitude of the effect among studies by weighting the effect size of each study. Weighting is a crucial element of meta-analysis and should be done by inverse variance. Other approaches, as for example by sample size, can lead to several problems as the introduction of unknown biases. Incorrect weights or the absence of weighting may cause an overestimation of effect sizes (Hungate et al., 2009).

Another problem is non-independence of effect sizes that occurs when multiple effect sizes are extracted from a single study. This can lead to erroneous conclusions as well. Thapa et al. (2018) recommended to report the measures of within-study variability such as standard deviation, standard error, and coefficient of variation to provide a quantitative data analysis. Also, Paradelo et al. (2015) stated that comparisons between studies are not easy to accomplish, due to the differences in site properties and experimental design. In this context, Haddaway et al. (2017) highlighted the importance to better document meta-analysis data and details on study design, experimental layout, agricultural soil management and pedoclimatic conditions in order to facilitate future analyses.

Knowledge gaps and research recommendations on modeling

Hansen et al. (2019) reported that simulation models can be useful tools to quantify N transformation and loss processes. In this context, they observed that limited studies based on field-scale experiments included all C and N turnover processes, such as loss of C and N from above-ground tissues and rhizodeposition. Similarly, in recent modelling studies Krauss et al. (2017) and Lugato et al. (2018) identified soil fluxes as one of the most uncertain components in large-scale modelling and they suggested that strategies to increase SOC sequestration might be offset by increased N₂O, depending on cropping systems and on the duration of the agricultural management practices. Recent progress in modelling SOC may help to better understand SOC dynamics, but at present the interaction between C and N cycles is still poorly represented in models (Guenet et al., 2021).

The implementation of mineralization and turnover algorithms in other models must be a priority to complement and upscale field observations under a range of soil and climatic conditions (Doltra et al., 2019). A better understanding of the interactions between management practices and biogeochemical C and N cycles is necessary to evaluate the benefits of different management practices aimed at increasing SOC storage and to predict the full GHG balance of each practice (Guenet et al., 2021). Moreover, measurements of N₂O emissions and N loss by NO₃ leaching should be conducted for at least a full year (Quemada et al., 2013; Basche et al., 2014) to allow a better modelling and prediction of the effects of soil management strategies on the trade-offs and synergies between SOC stock changes and these parameters (Dignac et al., 2017).

4.3 Limitations of this report

Despite the unique character of this report, some limitations need to be considered. In order to maximize the geographic spread of the literature that was collected, literature from institutional libraries was collected in the first instance in English language, but not in other European languages. In combination with the search restrictions, and the focus on reviews and meta-analyses, as well as original articles on trade-offs, this makes that recent literature relevant for some pedo-climatic zones may not be considered. Original articles, which had the objective to study the effects of one of the four management strategies on either SOC or GHG emissions and/or N leaching loss separately, remained outside the scope of this report. We acknowledge that the number of such articles may reach several hundreds, making it difficult to summarize them in a narrative report. Research performed in e.g., the very eastern countries of Europe may be underrepresented in this study, despite the large agricultural areas in those regions. In addition, not all soil management strategies identified in Table 1 were described in this report and require further research.

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SOMMIT WP2: Identification of knowledge gaps and literature review

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